

COCOREADO H2020 PROJECT

FOOD SYSTEM INNOVATOR TOOLKIT

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Introduction

This Toolkit is a collection of practical tools, useful tips, and sources of inspiration to support innovation towards re-connecting consumers and producers, to rebalance farmers' position in Food Supply Chains.

The materials found in the Toolkit have been brought together and validated within the HORIZON 2020 project COCOREADO, designed to rebalance the position of the farmer as an individual actor, a key player in innovative food supply chains, and a supplier for public procurement. The project has involved both academic and farming community partners across Europe, recognising regional differences and barriers (in terms of replicability of good practices) and regional opportunities (in terms of solutions).

A substantial part of the project has been building and maintaining the COCOREADO Ambassador Network of 40 young people passionate about food and agriculture, who are willing to facilitate sustainable changes in food systems. You can learn more about the [COCOREADO ambassadors community here](#).

The material you find in the Toolkit has been validated with these ambassadors over a two-year period, in face-to-face trainings and beyond.

By clicking on the links that you find within the Toolkit you can access other related sources and materials.

Chapters

[The Toolkit consists of five chapters:](#)

DEVELOPING NETWORKS

This chapter aims to define the most important elements to be considered when designing and developing a network to facilitate change within food systems. Practical steps and experiences from developing the COCOREADO Ambassador Network are offered as an example for developing a long-term network of food system innovators.

GETTING INSPIRED FROM EXAMPLES

This chapter focuses on different ways that good practices can be identified and studied, and ways that their lessons can be applied to improve food systems in different contexts and regions.

COMMUNICATING CHANGE

This chapter outlines key elements for developing effective communication, provides practical communication tips, and gives in-depth insights on communication through selected contemporary channels, such as social media, video, and podcasts.

ENGAGING WITH POLICY

This chapter explores ways that the agenda setting phase can be influenced from a bottom-up perspective. Here you will find information on how to:

- Establish policy-oriented communication;
- Produce a policy brief;
- Prepare a policy workshop;
- Address and engage with a local urban food policy.

DEVELOPING AN IDEA INTO BUSINESS

In this chapter, the tools used in the COCOREADO ambassador training programme, with the aim of developing seed initiatives, are presented. It covers everything from fleshing out a preliminary idea to an initial definition of the business model.

You can either get acquainted with the chapters in the order they have been presented, or easily jump to the sections that interest you most.

When getting familiar with the material, you may encounter the following abbreviations:

CAP Common Agricultural Policy

COCOREADO Connecting consumers and producers to rebalance farmers' position

CSA Community supported agriculture

EU European Union

FAO Food and Agriculture Organisation

LFS Local food system

NGO Non-governmental organisation

NOFA Novel and fair food system good practice

NPO Non-profit organisation

OECD Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

SFSC Short food supply chain

UFS Urban food strategy

Organisations involved

The following organisations have contributed to the development of the Food System Innovator toolkit:

BSC
Nodibinajums Baltic
Studies Centre

CEJA
European Council of
Young Farmers

CONSULAI
Consultoria
Agroindustrial LDA

INI
Iniciativas
Innovadoras SAL

EV ILVO
Flanders Research
Institute for Agricultural
and Fisheries Research

INTIA
Institute for Agri-food
Technology and
Infrastructures of Navarre

IPS
Institute of Philosophy
and Sociology

JSI
Jozef Stefan Institute

KU LEUVEN
University of Leuven

LUT
Lappeenrannana-Lahden
Teknillinen Yliopisto LUT

MIJARC
Jozef Stefan Institute

RYEUROPE
Rural Youth Europe EV

UCPH
University of Copenhagen

We hope this material offers you some inspiration and new ideas!

For any further inquiries regarding the material presented or the project please contact us via e-mail:

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COCOREADO H2020 PROJECT

FOOD SYSTEM INNOVATOR TOOLKIT

CH1 Developing Networks

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- 1 Why networks matter
- 2 Steps of building a network
- 3 How to facilitate a network
- 4 Sharing skills and knowledge
- 5 How to maintain a network?

1.1- Why networks matter

There are people trying to make a difference [in food systems] in every part of Europe. By coming together, we can have a greater impact.

Participant of COCOREADO Ambassador Network

This toolkit section aims to define the most important elements to be considered when designing and developing a network to facilitate change.

When it comes to facilitating change in food systems, bringing together a group of individuals who share a similar goal can increase the expected impact in several different ways, such as:

- Knowledge exchange, including knowledge on food supply chain and policy influencing
- Gaining inspiration for new projects from other group members
- Learning and receiving support from professionals in the field
- Combining and integrating different interests in novel food initiatives, therefore making them also more inclusive
- Sharing skills (e.g. communication or business skills) and best practices (e.g. sharing experience with innovative green start-ups, building food hubs, building sustainable farms)

Figure 1. The impact of developing an international network of change-makers on local food systems.

During the [COCOREADO project](#), an ambassador network was built by involving people with a common goal of helping connect consumers and farmers to rebalance farmers' position in food supply chains. Within this network:

- 40 ambassadors from throughout Europe are involved
- 6 seed initiatives to facilitate change were being developed
- 3 face-to-face trainings for the ambassadors took place in three different parts of Europe
- The ambassadors' knowledge was deployed to define good practices to change food systems
- The experience from building the ambassador network has been further used to help the ambassadors build their local networks for making positive impact on local and regional food systems.

Figure 2. Elements of COCOREADO Ambassador Network.

The COCOREADO ambassador network is used in this chapter to exemplify different steps of building and maintaining a network for facilitating change.

The next section gives an overview of building and maintaining a network, including a description of step-by-step activities taken to build a network and highlighting possible challenges that might be encountered in the network-building and maintenance process.

1.2- Steps of building a network

If you want to change something, one of the most important things is bringing people together. There are many people with very good ideas, but there is not all the expertise and all the practicalities, and the skills in one person. If you want to change something, you will need to bundle forces. Do that over generations, do that across disciplines, do that with academics together with non-academics.

*Tessa Avermaete, project coordinator
KU Leuven, Belgium*

Some networks for facilitating change may grow naturally out of a group that shares common interests or an organisation such as an NGO that has set a certain goal and field of interest. However, while these networks are often effective at local levels, it is more challenging to develop a network of change-makers at an international level, involving people who have not had any professional ties before, that could bring further impact and new knowledge to the local level agri-food systems.

In the case of COCOREADO, the intention of the ambassador network was to bring together young people from across Europe who represent the whole food supply chain to build their capacity for facilitating change in food systems through reconnecting consumers and producers.

For this purpose, a step-by-step plan for the development and consolidation of the COCOREADO ambassador network was deployed (see information on the following page).

BUILDING COCOREADO AMBASSADORS' NETWORK

THE ROLE OF COCOREADO AMBASSADORS - HELPING REBALANCE FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN AND REBUILD CONNECTION BETWEEN FARMERS AND CONSUMERS IN EUROPE

1

ANNOUNCING THE PROGRAMME AND OPENING THE APPLICATION PROCESS

- Setting clear requirements for ambassadors' profiles
- Announcing the ambassador programme via the website and personal networks

SELECTION PROCESS OF COCOREADO AMBASSADORS

Selection criteria: experience with food systems, engagement in the local community, communication skills, reasons and motivation for applying

2

3

ANNOUNCING THE RESULTS OF THE SELECTION AND ORGANISING THE FIRST ONLINE MEETING

- Individual emails to the applicants
- First online meeting: introduction to the project, programme's goals, next steps.

BUILDING PATHWAYS FOR COMMUNICATING ONLINE

- Using 'Slack' platform for communication with and among the ambassadors
- Creating network-specific channels (#cocoreado-official, #ideas-collaboration, #seed initiatives etc.)

4

5

FIRST AMBASSADORS' TRAINING

- Networking via formal training events: lectures, site visits, and group work
- Informal networking activities: sharing meals and coffee breaks, energizers

ACTIVITIES IN-BETWEEN THE TRAININGS

- Voting, selecting, and developing seed initiatives
- Informative sessions on skills development (pitching with impact) and practical topics (precision farming)

6

7

SECOND AND THIRD AMBASSADORS' TRAININGS

- Second training: focus on the seed initiatives. Working with the collaboration model
- Third training: ambassadors choose among three training tracks

The first three steps refer to the activities aimed towards **setting up the network**. Precise decisions in these steps regarding aspects of network development, such as **clearly defining the aims of the network and selecting highly motivated people** with common goals and diverse backgrounds, are crucial for the future network to operate smoothly and bring change to the food systems at both local and international levels. In addition to defining a common goal, there are variables that influence stronger cohesion and effective work of the future network, such as **age, gender diversity, and common professional background**, so these variables should be considered when creating a network.

The fourth step, **building communication channels**, is necessary to ensure that communication between members of the network can happen flawlessly during the ambassador trainings, and even more importantly, in between face-to-face meetings. **Regular communication possibilities**, especially between distant participants in the international context, are also crucial for building and maintaining a sense of belonging to the network. In our case, we chose to use “Slack” as a platform for communication; however, communication via e-mail and later through a WhatsApp group were still mostly preferred by the participants. Therefore, we advise introducing any new tools and apps cautiously and mindfully of participants' digital skills and willingness to use new communication tools for networking.

The last three steps include different **face-to-face and online activities** that brought the participants of the network together and allowed them to find common ground for discussions, reflect on the local challenges of the food systems, find possible solutions, and learn from each other's ideas and experience. These steps are crucial in allowing the participants to get to know each other and build new professional connections.

The last and final step is **supporting the evolution of the network beyond** the project lifetime (find more about this step in part 2.5. “How to maintain a network”).

1.3- How to facilitate a network

I have had the opportunity to know different people from different parts of Europe. And I realise that each region has its own features. This has been rewarding!

Participant of COCOREADO Ambassador Network

“

A network can only fulfil its purpose if it is **cohesive, focused, and proactive** as much as it is **productive**. To achieve and maintain these qualities of a network, necessary efforts must be made in its facilitation. Facilitation involves recognition of both the entire network's and individual participants' needs, aspirations, and resources.

On the next page you can find the practical elements that should be taken care of when facilitating a network's activity and growth for an extended period of time (which will have several distinctions from facilitating networking for a one-time event or activity).

MANAGING THE NETWORK: ROLES AND RESPONSABILITIES

Internal communication

Assigning a contact person between the project and the network (or among the network of participants, if the network has been built in a different setting outside the project framework) for delivering messages to the network members.

Messages should be communicated well in advance before expected actions (e.g. participation in an online or face-to-face event, filling out a survey), with the possibility for members of the network to reach out in case of any questions and comments.

Planning and organising face-to-face and/or online events

Planning the event agenda, speakers, and visits of local sites (in case of face-to-face trainings) and aligning them with the overall goals of the network is a task that needs dedicated time and resources.

It's better to take up planning of events as a group rather than alone, as it leaves room for brainstorming of ideas and ensures that a single person does not get overwhelmed with tasks.

Facilitating trainings/events

When the agenda of the event has been laid out, it is important to ensure that the overall event will be facilitated by dedicated people who keep the flow of the event going and help to establish and maintain the overall thread of the event.

External communication

If the goal of the network is to facilitate change, external communication channels are crucial.

COCOREADO ambassador network had established [social media accounts on YouTube, Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram](#).

You can read more about these communication tools in Chapter 4 of the Toolkit, "Communicating Change".

Administrative tasks and practicalities

If the network activities are funded by a project, as in the case of the COCOREADO project, there must be dedicated staff undertaking the administrative and financial tasks, especially in the case of organising face-to-face events that involve considerable costs for renting the event premises, accommodation, and travelling.

Monitoring the network and adapting to change

A network of people does not tend to stay as a static entity; sometimes the participants change or new needs emerge. It is essential to gather feedback from the participants regularly and adjust the planned activities to the expectations of the participants.

For a network to be **cohesive**, it is essential that its individual members relate to the purpose of the network in such a way **that everyone wants to be a fundamental part of a more complex system**. This recognition of the network's overall objective allows individuals, even if they come from different settings and countries, to connect with a common goal that brings them closer together. To ensure that each member of the network feels more connected with others, it is useful to share the profiles of all network members, including their experience and goals, with others.

To be **focused and proactive** as much as it is **productive**, the network must be stimulated to deliver results that respond to the common need identified as the overall objective. It is important to create routines within the network and not allow it to become disconnected, whether in terms of interaction between individuals in the network, or in terms of proposing tasks that gradually create content and results. It should not be forgotten that the level of knowledge within the network must always be increasing so that the individuals themselves feel motivated to remain in the network, and that being part of the network also provides them with added value.

For instance, the members of the COCOREADO Ambassador Programme took part in three consecutive trainings, and each training was followed by a **survey** to monitor their benefits from the programme and future needs. Each **training was gradually adjusted** to the ambassadors' expectations, while also keeping the initially pre-defined overall goal of the network (connecting consumers and producers to rebalance farmers' position in the food system) in focus. Additionally, at the beginning of the trainings, the ambassadors received a **student binder** that, in addition to the agenda, provided the most important concepts, methods, and materials used in the training.

Once the initial group of change-makers has been formed and you have a clear idea for future activities, how do you ensure that the chosen group of people becomes a "network"?

Two characteristics are defined as essential for the network of people to form:

- They should have a **common interest, goal, or concern**
- They should keep a **remaining connection** with each other that is maintained through interaction, assistance, and support

Finally, for the previous two characteristics to remain stable, it is also highly recommended that a network operates **in a systematic way**. For instance, there is a set number of online and/or face-to-face meetings per year and the network is regularly updated on news and events via chosen communication channels.

SUCCESSFUL NETWORK

Figure 3. Key features of a successful network

In addition to these three core characteristics, we have named **other qualities and characteristics** that we have found to be essential **for a successful network** to form, based on our experience:

Figure 4. Characteristics that enable the forming of a successful network

How can you ensure that these pre-conditions are met and the networking takes place in a way that benefits the involved professionals and helps reach the chosen goal of the network? Below we give a **checklist of essential tools for keeping the network active within a two-year period.**

Once the network is created, it needs to be nurtured using some important tools such as:

- Team building (e.g. team building activities to get to know other participants, informal events of sharing local food and common meals, working in groups according to similar interests)
- Dividing long-term goals into smaller tasks achievable in the short-term (e.g. tackling 1-2 specific objectives and topics per session to be more productive)
- Create a trust environment where everybody can share inputs (e.g. setting simple rules prior to the events that highlight the network's values, such as respectful and active listening, openness to new ideas, and appreciation for experiences from different local contexts)
- Delegate responsibility (e.g. offer network participants to facilitate workshops and conduct sessions on project activities)

Challenging to facilitate workshops & conducting sessions

Figure 5. Tools to nurture a network that is already operating

1.4- Sharing skills and knowledge

The ambassadors approach is powerful and the mixed group of participants makes for really interesting discussions and is a great way to learn and grow.

Participant of COCOREADO Ambassador Network

We have identified and brought together a group of young people who all want to change the system but, on their own, none of them could probably do it. Or some of them already had ideas, but then we brought them together with other, like-minded people. And I think that's the strongest thing to be able to, to feel like, 'Hey, I'm not alone!' That gives some kind of emotional, psychological consolidation. And then you also have these like-minded people give you advice on your ideas.

Mirentxu Asín Irurozqui, project communications officer
INICIATIVAS INNOVADORAS, Spain

One of the main purposes of building the COCOREADO network was to raise its participants' capacity for facilitating change in agri-food systems through knowledge sharing and skill development. We include formal and informal types of activities that have aided in sharing skills and knowledge across the COCOREADO network, including knowledge-sharing among the ambassadors and involving both the ambassadors and project partners (see Figure 6).

FACILITATING KNOWLEDGE-SHARING AND NETWORKING

FORMAL AND INFORMAL ACTIVITIES TO AID THE KNOWLEDGE-SHARING WITHIN THE NETWORK

Figure 6. Examples of formal and informal activities to aid the knowledge-sharing within the network

While not all networking and knowledge-sharing within the network is always a result of deliberate efforts, various activities can be used to facilitate the exchange of skills and knowledge between participants. **Working in teams** can be used to work on more narrow topics that interest a certain group of participants, as well as to work on certain business ideas that the participants already have. Similarly, **parallel sessions** (online or face-to-face) are a way for smaller groups of participants to get more immersed in certain topics related to food systems. In between different learning activities, some brief **team-building activities** can be used, which are a less formal way to connect and learn more about each other. Similarly, **social events** such as social dinners and local food-sharing events are opportunities to get to know each other in more informal settings in the case of face-to-face meetings.

Meanwhile, **learning from showcases** is another excellent way of knowledge-gathering about innovative regional efforts of rebalancing the farmers' position within the food system. Within the COCOREADO project, this was done in the form of cross-visits ([Read more about the cross-visit approach in Chapter "Getting inspired from examples"](#)).

Capturing the impact of the network on its participants is always a challenging task. Not all impact can be measured in an objective way immediately, since some knowledge and skills, as well as contacts gained, may prove useful for participants in the longer term. However, surveys and other forms of feedback can help to get an overview of the skills and knowledge gained that the participants have found most valuable. Figure 7 represents some of the skills and new knowledge that have been highlighted by COCOREADO ambassadors.

- Cross-cultural and interdisciplinary communication skills
- Communication in social media
- Awareness of the food system operation and regional challenges in other regions
- Using Business Model Canvas to develop a business model
- Knowledge about market power and value distribution
- Knowledge about public procurement, including dynamic procurement
- How to design a food strategy at the local level
- How to use decision support tools

Figure 7. Some of the skills and knowledge gained during the trainings of the network (feedback from the participants of the COCOREADO network)

Additionally, the exchange of knowledge between the network's participants, if a network is built at an international level or has gathered specialists from different regions within a country, is a great source of information about local particularities of food systems. For instance, the diversity of the COCOREADO network has also helped to enrich the project as such, so much so that some conclusions and results would not have been so easy to gather if it hadn't been for the existing network. The project, since it is **transversal to many European regions**, had its work developed considering various food production systems which were more easily perceived by the diversity of individuals who are part of the network.

1.5- How to maintain a network?

Challenges of building and maintaining a network

While the network offers significant benefits, the following list contains an overview of challenges that were encountered within the COCOREADO project and should also be kept in mind when developing any other network for change. The overview also includes possible solutions to these challenges.

CHALLENGE	POSSIBLE SOLUTION
Recruiting participants that would be a good fit for the project and the programme.	A very focused call for participants. The call for participants is disseminated through project partners' networks from all over.
Involving representatives of the whole system	A call for participants that could be interesting for a wide range of professionals within the field. Focus on diversity during the selection process.
Maintaining internal activity and visibility of the network	Involving professionals to facilitate communication activities within and outside of the network.
Maintaining ongoing interest	Development of an engaging training programme that would be interesting for young people from across Europe. Focus on both the newest research in the field and topical issues for the target group. Linking activities to real-life situations and challenges and demonstrating impact.
Development of relevant skills	Focusing on the ambassadors' needs and doing a constant monitoring of their change. Developing an open, bonding relationship with the involved participants and identifying a) the necessary skills b) ways to develop these skills.

Plan for maintaining a network

Sometimes networks for change are built within projects with a limited time frame. However, once the network has been set into action, the goal is for it to keep functioning beyond a project's lifetime. This can be a challenging task; therefore, we share our insights into possible steps and activities to be taken to ensure that the network keeps functioning beyond the project's lifetime.

After the last ambassador training, we encouraged the network of ambassadors to select **ambassador representatives** who would become a point of contact between the ambassador network and the project. The next step was to gradually put more responsibility in ambassadors' hands. The ambassadors were provided with **a template for a plan** for continuing the ambassadors' network which you can find below. The template can be used at different stages of the network forming process.

Following the template, the participants of the COCOREADO network (the ambassadors) came up with their vision and mission statements, as well as a list of future activities that can serve as an example for other networks.

The vision

"Cocoreado envisions a sustainable and equitable food system in Europe where producers and consumers are seamlessly connected, and the balance of power in the food supply chain is restored. We see a future where knowledge exchange is the driving force, empowering farmers and consumers alike."

The mission

"Our mission is to create a vibrant and diverse network of passionate food ambassadors from across Europe. We strive to uncover, evaluate, and promote best practices for direct selling and short food supply chains. Our commitment is to spread these innovative concepts throughout all European countries through our ambassador community, fostering a dynamic, knowledge-driven ecosystem. We also engage with stakeholders at all levels to drive positive change in the European food landscape."

The envisioned future activities include:

- Online problem-solving meetings (discussions with experts about selected topics)
- COCOREADO Summit (annual physical conference for networking, offering services, and showcasing the work of COCOREADO)
- Growing and intensifying partnerships and approaching new strategic partners
- Organising trainings and workshops for small scale farmers and producers

Considering the organisational structure of the future network, the participants have created an **NPO (non-profit organisation), COCOREADOx**, that serves as a formalised network that can offer services and apply for future funding.

The board of the NPO consists of: A chair, a secretary, a treasurer and a vice chair. Two auditors have been also elected to assist the board in its oversight to safeguard the organization's financial integrity.

Questions:

What is the vision of the Ambassador Network?

Why are you doing what you are doing? What is the long term change you want to realise?

Eg: we want to make the European food system fairer for farmers, healthier for consumers and in balance with the environment.

What activities do you plan to organise?

Do you want to offer services? What kind?

What kind of activities do you plan to organise for the Ambassadors? Online events, physical events? On which topics? Organised by whom?

How do you plan to finance these activities?

Will you ask of a membership fee? Will you look for public or private funding?

Do you know what your expenses will be? What the revenues will be?

Organisational structure

Is the network open to all ambassadors? Also to new ambassadors? What are the requirements to be allowed to join?

How will you make decisions?

What kind of tasks need to be carried out? How will you divide the tasks?

Do you need a legal entity? What kind of entity would you prefer?

What is the mission of the Ambassador Network?

What will you do to achieve this mission?

Eg: We connect diverse local actors from all over Europe to stimulate an open debate between citizens and local governments.

Figure 8. The template that the Ambassadors received

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CH2 Getting inspired from examples

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- 2 Finding and identifying good practices
- 3 Learning from good practices
- 4 Pairing international evidence with local context
- 5 Cross visits and other sources of good practices

2.1- Introduction

Food system transformations that better connect consumers and farmers are achieved through novel food initiatives and practices, which reconfigure existing relationships or generate new relationships between food chain actors. Food systems, their contexts, situations, and needs, vary greatly. This means that specific solutions might be needed to improve their sustainability. In the meantime, there is a range of existing solutions: **effective novel food initiatives that can be adapted**, and from which helpful lessons can be learned. This chapter focuses on different ways that good practices can be identified and studied, and how their lessons can be applied to improve food systems in different contexts and regions.

For a network to serve as a sufficient ground for learning, there must be a systematic and effective approach to collecting, sharing, and analysing pre-existing practices. This chapter will focus on different ways that learning from good practices can be implemented by food system innovators for maximum benefit. There will be a particular focus on **good practices in novel and fair food systems (NOFAs)** that COCOREADO ambassadors were working with.

What are novel and fair food systems (NOFAs)?

(Local) food systems which (re)connect consumers and producers and/or strengthen the position of the farmer in the food chain.

Figure 1. The definition of novel and fair food systems (NOFAs).

“Good practices” refer to sustainable activities and initiatives that have proven to be effective and bring about expected results in combatting pre-defined problems. Nowadays, food systems face a range of challenges (see Figure 2).

The challenges agri-food systems face:

Macro perspective:

- (1) Climate change,
- (2) Price volatility,
- (3) Asymmetric market power,
- (4) Food safety,
- (5) Declining consumer trust.

Figure 2. The challenges agri-food systems face.

To address these challenges, one needs to account for **the complex human-environmental character of food systems**. This includes a variety of components such as environment, people, institutions, processes, and actors (from producers to consumers), and activities such as food production, distribution, and consumption. Food systems also have different drivers, such as: biophysical and environmental; technology and infrastructure; political and economic; sociocultural and demographic (Brouwer, McDermott and Ruben (2020)) (See Figure 3).

Figure 3. The elements of the complex human-environmental character of food systems. of COCOREADO Ambassador Network.

The COCOREADO project focused specifically on **the problem of disconnected producers and consumers**. As agri-food supply chains have become longer and include more actors, the distance between the primary producers and consumers has increased. This has created a gap between them, including a communication gap, as farmers sell their products to intermediaries and lack contact with final consumers. Consequently, this means that farmers are not aware of opportunities to improve their offers and adapt to demand. At the same time, consumers lack information on the origin of the food they eat. Therefore, the project’s specific interest in existing good practices was focused on their potential to combat longer and more globalized food chains, communication gaps between consumers and producers, poor opportunities for producers to adapt their offers to consumers’ demand, and lack of information for consumers about the food they consume (see Figure 4).

What COCOREADO wants to combat

Figure 4. Finding the focus of the good practices through analysing the challenges they are trying to combat.

Across Europe, there are numerous examples that demonstrate concrete ways for farmers to collaborate on opportunities that are both consumer-driven and conducive to improving farmers’ incomes. How to find them?

2.2- Finding and identifying good practices

Defining the focus of the good practices you are looking for

Once you are clear about the problems you wish to address in your food system, you can specify whom the good practices you are seeking are meant for, and what their purpose is. For instance, the COCOREADO project has had **a focus on youth, with an aim to contribute to the development of novel and fair food systems**. This goal was achieved **through the identification of good practices** based on **success factors**. These good practices can be further exploited and disseminated, for instance, through activities with dedicated ambassadors and co-creation with local actors.

Figure 5. The approach and integration of good practices within the COCOREADO project

For the project's purposes, good practices were considered within **NOFAs or (local) food systems in which innovative collaborations between farmers and other food system actors occur, which includes practices that connect consumers and producers to overcome unfair trading practices and rebalance the farmers' position**. More specifically, these are collaborations that can make use of economies of scale, smarter distribution, reduction of environmental footprints, territorial approaches, etc., to improve farmers' income. An example of novel food systems is sharing the farmer's risk with consumers while reconnecting farmers and consumers, such as in community supported agriculture.

Small farmers can strengthen their position by creating added value in terms of products or services offered. In this context, increased consumer concern about sustainable food can be regarded as an opportunity for small farmers.

In this case, one main element to look for when considering whether a particular example can serve as a good practice is if it contributes to the overall transformation towards sustainable and fair food systems. **Fair food systems** are referred to as **innovative ways for farmers to collaborate with each other**, as well as with intermediaries and other parties, on opportunities aiming to connect consumers and farmers, improve farmers' income, and strengthen farmers' position in the food chain.

As part of this innovative way to collaborate, you can encounter **a set of concrete practices that focus on the end result of a supply chain collaboration (SCC), supporting the success of NOFAs**. Each good practice is defined by one or several **success factors** – elements of action through which it has contributed to building a more sustainable food system.

Selection process of good practices

For the process of selecting the good practices, it is crucial to develop clear criteria. Figure 6 offers an overview of selection criteria used within the COCOREADO project for pre-selecting the innovative initiatives. With the help of these criteria, within the COCOREADO project [an initial list of 61 good practices](#) was gathered by project partners from different parts of Europe. You can use this list to consider other good practices within your own country/region, or use it as an example to develop your own list of criteria.

Figure 6. An example of the list of criteria to be used when identifying good practices.

Information sheet with criteria for pre-selecting innovative initiatives together with all partners

Strengthening the position of the farmer

Refers to farmers achievements within a supply chain collaboration. Did the farmer improve his/her economic position by using this specific collaboration?

Improving the connection between producer and consumer

Refers to the establishment of connectedness between producers and consumers. Did the farmer establish a more direct relationship with his/her consumers? Do both farmer and consumer share knowledge, value and meaning about the product and its provenance, production and consumption? Is there a mutual understanding of producers/consumers on needs and mutual benefits.

Potential of scaling-up/replicability

Do you think this case has the potential to be replicated or to be scaled up?:

- Do you think the case has potential to grow/scale-up in its current form and context?
- Do you think similar cases can be set up in its own country?
- Do you think this case can be replicated in other contexts and countries?

Willingness of key informants to cooperate (excluding criterion)

Please think about and share your expert perception about the willingness of the key actors from the initiative to be pre-selected to further cooperate with the project. Do you think actors from the initiative you suggested would be willing to share information about their practices. E.g. through an interview or a visit to the farm/shop/market?

Selection process of good practices

Further, from the initial list of good practices, **14 NOFAs** were examined more closely. These 14 cases, that were selected from across Europe, illustrate good practices and success factors leading to benefits for farmers, consumers, and broader local communities. The common element between these 14 cases is that **they represent fair short food supply chains**, which become successful and sustainable thanks to meaningful cooperation between farmers, producers, and other actors along the food chain, all striving to shorten the distance between production and consumption.

You can get acquainted with the short list of NOFAs gathered within the project [here!](#)

2.3- Learning from good practices

The identified good practices and their key success factors serve as a guide for new initiatives. They have been validated with COCOREADO ambassadors who are experts in their field and they capture the diversity of initiatives across Europe.

*Rui Almeida
CONSULAI, Portugal*

When considering any novel initiative gathered within the COCOREADO project, or one that you know in your own region, the question remains of how to break down the elements of success and how they can serve as learning points for new and inspiring initiatives. In COCOREADO, the practices were grouped based on a common success factor identified as the key aspect of that practice.

Below you can find a list of **10 common success factors** that have been identified.

1 Success factor: Transparency and availability of information

Key aspect to **establish trust**.

- Being able to visit the farm producing the products purchased, and/or having the producer available in the selling location.
- Sharing a profile of farmers that are part of the initiative, so that consumers “know the face” of the people that are producing their food.
- Direct contact with end customers.
- The trust aspect is mentioned in very different types of NOFAs. Even when there are formal agreements, there is always a mention of trust between supply chain partners. NOFAs that sell products from more than one farmer often operate as a sort of quality label. Consumers may want organic, fair, local produce, but don't have time to check for this with every product they buy. Once they trust the NOFA, they know that all products purchased there are organic and fair.

2 Success factor: Engagement of the value-chain

Key aspect to **connect producers and consumers**.

- Both consumers and producers have an integral role in the initiative through an association or cooperative, through which they are represented by members who have decision-making powers.
- Exploring ways to maintain the importance of the community aspect and to attract local people.
- Setting up a collaboration with other farmers that ensures that all farmers can determine their own price but are incentivized to deliver good quality products on time.
- The initiator has autonomy over different parts of the lifecycle of the product, including production, packaging, and delivery within the initiative.

3 Success factor: Strategic production planning

Key aspect to **reduce food waste at the farm- and consumer-level, while maintaining a competitive advantage.**

- The farmer can easily acquire knowledge on market demand and adjust their production
- accordingly, thanks to a closer relationship between producer and consumer.
- Experimenting with more and different crops.
- To help farmers plan ahead, implement a subscription model for consumers, where they can choose the frequency with which they order.

4 Success factor: Multidisciplinary partnership

Key aspect to **ensure a comprehensive approach that can maximise success.**

- Establishing long-term partnerships with public and/or private entities can give greater support in resources, finances, and training. This can include the support of the municipality or government.
- Combining the initiative with a network of various food-related activities can bring profitability (e.g., restaurants, shops, agri-tourism).
- Partners of the initiative are responsible for collecting products from farmers; less travelling minimizes environmental and economic costs.

5 Success factor: Goal congruence

Key aspect to **ensure that all parts are satisfied.**

- A common goal gives the participants a shared purpose and encourages them to work together as a team to achieve an end result.
- Consumers or participants have a similar vision, mission, and values.

6 Success factor: Financial resources/company structure

Key aspect for **financial longevity.**

- Applying for funding (e.g., LIFE funding, subsidies).
- Crowd funding to kickstart a project.
- Having more than one income source, so that the new initiative is only part of the total farm income.
- Adjusting financial goals to the initiative structure; a non-profit organisation has different goals than a private farmer.

7 Success factor: Define target market

Key aspect to **ensure likelihood of purchase.**

- Recognition of customer needs.
- Using market segmentation to your advantage (middle- or high-income families, families with children, retirees, consumers who are ecologically conscious). This type of initiative usually focuses on a market niche.

8 Success factor: Quality certification and/or focus on high quality

Key aspect to **differentiate offer**.

- Innovative product (e.g., products from vertical farming in a city using controlled environmental agriculture).
- Offering local products.
- High-end product: focus on higher quality. Customer is aware the product might be more expensive due to its characteristics.

9 Success factor: External communication

Key aspect to **build brand awareness**.

- Participation in different marketplaces, such as fairs, events, and catering.
- Use of communication tools to interact with consumers, such as newsletters, APPs, and web-based platforms.
- Communication strategy: A clear and strong story, from product-based to story-based marketing. Uniqueness is important.

10 Success factor: Personality and skills of the initiators

Key aspect for a **business mentality**.

- Founders share the same goal and common motivation (innovation, food, sustainability).
- Founders have different backgrounds.
- Founders are passionate and curious.
- Education level of the initiators on areas related to the agricultural sector and/or business management.
- Communication between initiators is well thought-out before starting the initiative. Define the communication tools to be used.
- A complementary team founding the initiative. In case of one initiator, there is an external board (e.g. consultants, advisors).
- Adapting the type of initiative to the personality of the farmers. For example, a community supported agriculture initiative (CSA) requires a lot of social interaction with customers. Vending machines do not require this.
- Knowledge/use of financial terms.
- Decision-making based on sales data or other financial data.
- Price-setting mechanisms to promote certain buying behaviour. For example, Landare supermarket takes lower margins on local products.

This list of good practices and success factors is complex and represents an ideal scenario for a fair and novel food system initiative. It is expected that no one initiative has all these factors, but rather an assortment, with some considered socially successful, economically successful, environmentally successful, or a combination.

2.4- Pairing international evidence with local context

Once the initiative has been recognized and assessed against pre-set criteria, and its success factors identified, it can be used as a tool for learning. Specifically, if you are passionate about fair food supply and are looking for an inspiring idea of how to turn your passion into action, you can learn from other successful initiatives that have inspired farmers, entrepreneurs, and local authorities across Europe. You can consider if an initiative and the innovative short food supply chain can be **replicated** in your respective region.

In the COCOREADO project, [replicability roadmaps](#) were developed to represent **14 successful initiatives that can serve as the first source of inspiration**. Each roadmap helps readers to learn about the main factors for the success of these initiatives. The roadmaps also include insights about what must be kept in mind if the readers want to replicate the success pathways in their own work.

[Watch the presentation video here.](#)

Figure 7. Overview of some of the replicability roadmaps, available on the website

The 14 cases were selected from across Europe and illustrate good practices and success factors leading to benefits for farmers, consumers, and broader local communities. The common element between the 14 cases is that they represent fair short food supply chains, which become successful and sustainable thanks to meaningful cooperation between farmers, producers, and other actors along the food chain, all striving to shorten the distance between production and consumption.

SELF-CHECK

Can you apply the Āgenskalna Market experience in your region?

YES	NO	Are you a representative of a municipality, association or private business interested in developing the city's historic places as meeting points between food producers and today's urban consumers with their increasingly diverse tastes and demand for local and fresh seasonal foods and various services?
YES	NO	Have you studied what is missing in the communication between food producers and consumers?
YES	NO	Have you thought about what strategy will be able to attract both small producers, offering seasonal food, and large traders, for whom many different customers come to the market every day?
YES	NO	Have you considered what other services you can offer at the market besides buying a wide variety of food?
YES	NO	Who would be your strategic partners with whom you can leverage different funding sources to grow the market as a kind of social fabric bringing creating vibrant urban communities?
YES	NO	Are you a leader/charismatic person able to create a devoted management team that is committed to developing the place as open and accessible to small and large producers and traders and to customers from different income groups?

Figure 8. Screenshot of a self-check list in one of the replicability roadmaps.

The roadmaps were created to learn about problems experienced by others, and to deliver knowledge about solutions, sources of funding, business models, good practices, and factors of success. To facilitate replication, the replicability **roadmaps include a self-checklist** to help you consider important elements when developing your ideas or planning your own solution.

Nevertheless, when considering the possibilities of replicating a good practice, you should also be mindful of the **possible challenges** related to the local context. Some of them have been listed below:

Replicability of a good practice

Possible challenges

- Access to information about the context of the local partners
- Local regulations
- Cross-cutting context in the EU
- Local subsidies
- Knowing your target audience/consumers and adapting your business strategy to them
- Cross-border barriers: administrative, digital platforms, decentralised databases

Apart from the overall challenges, it is worth considering additional challenges related to the replicability of the good practice in a particular context. For instance, you might want to consider the availability of infrastructure, existing strategic planning of agricultural production at local and regional levels, consumer awareness and demand, and other similar aspects.

Despite the aforementioned challenges, we encourage you to first look at the opportunities that replication of the good practices may represent and use the developed roadmaps and other good practices as a source of inspiration to bring positive change to the local context.

2.5- Cross visits and other sources of good practices

While the roadmaps represent one way to learn about good practices, there are also other sources of inspiration that can be beneficial for you and your team. Among these, **cross-visits** provide an opportunity to learn while visiting the actual setting of a good practice.

1. Cross visits

I think the cross visits are extremely important. Go together and see what is there, listen to people and then exchange information. What do you like, what do you dislike? That's something that I would certainly take up in the future again. So people can really see with their feet on the ground what a project looks like, and what kind of things people struggle with. And those can be personal things as well, those can be marketing things, ethical things, ideas, or ideals that people have.

*Tessa Avermaete, project coordinator
KU LEUVEN, Belgium*

The methodology for the COCOREADO cross-visits is modelled on the NEFERTITI and Agrispin method. This approach is based on a two-day visit which includes the kick-off, demonstrations, reflections, a social activity, and knowledge exchange.

Figure 8. NEFERTITI cross-visit approach, available in 'CROSS VISIT GUIDELINES TO ON FARM DEMONSTRATIONS'.

Figure 9. COCOREADO three-step approach for a cross-visit.

Considering the limited time available in the Ambassadors Training, three simple steps were implemented, modelled after the NEFERTITI and Agrispin approach.

Step 1 - Kick-off (15min)

GETTING ACQUAINTED:

- Introduction of the cross-visit purpose to the host.
- Introduction of the cross-visit host (by the host).

GETTING ORIENTED: Before the cross-visit, the questions below should be answered and addressed during this stage.

1. What are you most curious about?
2. What kind of answers would you like to take home after this visit?
3. How would you like to use these answers for your own work in your network?
4. What specific experience or knowledge would you like to share?

If a flyer for the initiative is available, it should be distributed before the visit.

Step 2 - Visit

Necessary materials:

- Notebooks and pens: distributed before the visit.

The participants must make sure they collect the necessary information. Therefore, cross-visit organisers should distribute materials where participants can write their doubts and relevant points to clarify in the next step.

Coffee-o'clock (10min): After the visit, a small break can take place to let the participants discuss what was visited. During this break, water and food should be provided.

Step 3 - Reflections

For this step, the required materials can vary depending on the exercise. Below we will provide an explanation for an exercise conducted in a cross-visit for the 3rd Ambassadors Training in Riga:

- Bingo card
- Notebooks
- Pens

There should be a sufficient number of facilitators, in addition to the host, to promote discussion among different participants. The timekeeper takes note of key aspects and ensures time management.

The exercise consists of a bingo card with the 10 success factors previously presented to the ambassadors (which are also present in this toolkit), as well as space to write down the good practices associated with the success factor. The objective is to engage with the host over the course of the visit, to discuss good practices and the potential to replicate them in their own local contexts.

Figure 10. A bingo card with 10 success factors that can be used during cross visits.

“I am very satisfied with the visit to **Getliņi Eko** enterprise, I saw for the first time the municipal garbage plant from where they get heat energy and then grow vegetables: cucumbers and tomatoes. It was amazing and very impressive, thank you for such an opportunity.”

Participant of COCOREADO Ambassador Programme

2. Other sources of good practices

While you are considering if organising a cross visit, or taking part in one, would be an available and beneficial option for you, below we provide a list of other useful sources that can provide you with extra inspiration and lead to other types of good practices!

1

Practices on Public Procurement (PROCURS)

Examples of public procurement practices in Europe to derive common solutions that can be implemented in future sustainable public procurements.

[MORE INFO](#)

2

The agroBRIDGES Toolbox

The agroBRIDGES Toolbox is a collection of 12 practical tools to support the growth of Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) in Europe and bring producers and farmers closer to consumers.

[MORE INFO](#)

3

COACH project's Communication, Learning and Innovation Platform (CLIP)

The CLIP hosts a searchable 'Living Library' of 34 [beacons](#). Each beacon tells a different story of how to shorten food chains and reconnect food producers and consumers. For each one, collaboration between actors has been of vital importance – the beacons showcased in our library bring together farmers, civil society, local authorities, and citizens with shared goals.

[MORE INFO](#)

4

Global network of lighthouse farms

A network of exemplary farms and foodscapes from around the world that have found radical solutions to address current sustainability challenges.

[MORE INFO](#)

5

Liaison project's Interactive Innovative Toolbox

Practical "How to Guides", newsletters, videos, reports and handbooks, policy briefs and conference papers.

[MORE INFO](#)

6

EIP-AGRI Operational Groups

Operational Groups are intended to bring together multiple actors such as farmers, researchers, advisers, businesses, environmental groups, consumer interest groups, or other NGOs to advance innovation in the agricultural and forestry sectors.

[MORE INFO](#)

7

EU CAP network: Forum of best practices

Enhance the cooperation between primary producers, improve their position within the food supply chain and increase market transparency.

[MORE INFO](#)

COCOREADO H2020 PROJECT

FOOD SYSTEM INNOVATOR TOOLKIT

CH3 Communicating change

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3.1- Introduction

Development of novel food initiatives involves engagement with other people: gaining visibility, reaching out to relevant stakeholders, and allying them with the initiative as informed citizens, active supporters, customers, or partners. Informing and persuading people, creating relationships, collaborative decision-making, and problem solving are all functions of communication. Hence, this chapter outlines key elements of **how to develop effective communication**, provides **practical communication tips**, and **gives in-depth insights on communication** through selected contemporary channels, such as social media, video, and podcasts.

3.2- Development of a Communication Plan

A Communication Plan is a support tool for reaching an organisation's goals through strategic outreach activities. It helps to identify, manage, and apply an organisation's communication resources in an organised and strategic manner in the medium- and long-term, in the most efficient and profitable way possible. It helps to optimise an organisation's resources through a series of communication actions planned over time and in the channels closest to its target audience.

A **Communication Plan involves several elements** and steps:

- **Objectives** or setting communication goals: Why do you want to communicate?
- **Audience** or identification of relevant target groups: Who needs to be communicated with?
- **Messages** or formulation of a message: What needs to be communicated?
- **Channels** or selection of appropriate communication channels: Where/How will the message be communicated?
- **Timing** or setting a communication timeline: When should this be communicated?
- Improvement or **monitoring and evaluation** of communication efficacy: How well is the message communicated? How many people will it reach?

Figure 1. Template of a communication plan.

Objectives

You must define **what you want to achieve** with the communication and outreach activities. Setting the objectives of the Communication Plan allows you to be clear about where you are heading and to develop communication activities accordingly. To achieve the best results, the objectives should be realistic in terms of what available resources will allow. This means that the objectives should be **SMART: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Time bound**.

Figure 2. The objectives set to achieve through communication must be SMART.

Audience

To communicate, you must clearly know **whom you are addressing** or what your target audience is. The target audience is the group of people who are the most relevant and interested in the implementation of the initiative, and its products and services. This group can influence, support, or benefit from it. The identified target audience or potential customers determine everything regarding the communication, starting from the chosen channels to the tone of communication; hence the importance of **defining who they are**. It is helpful to learn about their communication habits, and habits in relation to the planned initiative, products, or services.

Messages

For the communicated message to be as effective as possible, it must be **consistent with the values** of the organisation and **respond to the needs of the defined target audience**. It should specify the main differentiating characteristics of the initiative, product, or service. The message must be **clear and precise**, with **language and tone appropriate** to the target audience.

Channel

The Communication Plan's channel strategy should detail concrete communication actions to implement, the communication objective each action contributes to, and on which channel, platform, or medium it will be communicated. Messages should be transmitted through channels **where the target audience is usually found**. Possible channels include email, newsletter, meeting in person, participation in events, social media, local mass media, and many others.

Timing

To develop a timeline for communication actions, you need to know what communication resources are available and decide **how they can be distributed in the most effective way** possible. Having an action plan allows you to organise each action over time, detailing the **chronogram or timing** of an organisation or initiative. In short, it describes exactly what you will do and when.

Keep in mind that when people receive multiple messages that do not seem relevant to them, they can begin to devalue these messages. To avoid this issue, make sure communication timing and frequency are aligned with your messages and stakeholder groups.

Improvement

The action plan must be **measurable**. Established control indicators, based on the set objectives and actions to be carried out, can help to quantify and monitor the results. Measuring communication results helps to evaluate efficacy. The **evaluation of results** should be performed **periodically** (weekly, monthly, or quarterly, for instance) and **methodically**, using the same monitoring methods and indicators depending on your initiative, project, organisation, and objectives.

3.3- Communication on social media

Social media provides a platform for organisations to reach out to their target audience, share and gather information, and build community.

The main purpose behind social media content is to:

- Increase brand awareness
- Generate leads: capture interest in a product or service
- Help learn more about customers from their feedback
- Potentially drive traffic to your website
- Assist in collaborations with influencers
- Give a human touch to your digital company
- Boost sales
- Establish more informal communication with potential clients
- Stay on top of all industry-related news
- Place you ahead of your competitors

But, how to have an impact on social media? Below are 5 rules to maximise your social media impact:

1 Create high-quality, versatile content

- High-quality content that would likely be shareable.
- Make sure your content reflects your values.
- Do not forget to include versatile content. Here are some ideas of what you can include:
- Images, memes, infographics, videos, quotes, GIFs, or attractive Instagram stories. Combine your visuals with some interesting captions and voila – you've got a winning combo!

2 Find your “authentic” voice and style

On social media (and the internet overall) **content and authenticity** must go hand in hand. Developing a **unique, memorable** voice and **style** is crucial. Your voice and style should directly **reflect your brand and mission**.

3 Use the right hashtags

Using the right hashtags can make or break your social media strategy and content reach. Hashtags can help you get your content in front of the right people at the right time.

Keep your hashtags **short and memorable** (unless there is an important one that doesn't comply with these “rules”). It is important to note that when it comes to using hashtags, the same things don't apply across all social media platforms.

4 Share testimonials and reviews

Sharing customer testimonials and reviews is not only great for days when you have nothing else to post, but is useful for **attracting potential clients** too.

5 Make your content interactive

Ask questions, include clear CTAs (Call to Action*), and create a welcoming social media profile by posting content that draws attention. The more **engaged** your audience is and the more they **comment and like** your posts, take part in discussions, and so on, the higher your brand's perceived value and trust are.

* A Call to Action (CTA) seeks to attract potential users until they become end customers through a link with a strong power of attraction.

Some extra tips when posting...

X (TWITTER)

- Limit to 1-2 hashtags per Tweet.
- Be conversational.
- Keep your copy short, easy, and attractive.
- Use images, GIFs, and/or videos whenever possible!

LINKEDIN

- Make your titles between 40 and 49 characters long.
- People like to read long-form content – up to 2,000 words long.
- Include pictures.
- Maximum 2 hashtags.

FACEBOOK

- No more than 100 characters.
- Pose a question, this works very well on Facebook.
- Share relevant images.
- Include a Call to Action, and a link.

INSTAGRAM

- Maintain a consistent feed of high-quality visuals.
- Stay on top of Instagram changes and updates.
- Use hashtags to boost content discovery (8-10).
- Include a Call to Action, a link, in your stories.

3.4- Oral communication and presentation

Strong verbal communication skills are important for everyone in their personal and professional life. When speaking clearly and confidently, you are much more likely to command the respect of others and build rapport. This is particularly important in business interactions. For verbal communication to be effective, it should be clear, relevant, concise, informative, and tactful in phrasing and tone.

Nonverbal communication elements such as posture, gestures, and facial expressions are also important factors in developing good verbal communication skills. Your outward appearance mirrors your inner mood. Good posture suggests confidence; stand neither at rigid attention nor with sloppy casualness, but upright with your weight equally distributed on each foot. Some movement may be helpful to hold listeners' attention or to increase emphasis, but constant shifting or pacing should be avoided.

Good speakers should make frequent eye contact with the audience, let their facial expression show their interest in the ideas they are presenting, dress in a way that is appropriate for the occasion, and keep their energy levels high.

Below you can find **7 effective verbal communication factors**:

1

Think before you speak

By organizing your thoughts in advance, you can eliminate many of the awkward pauses that occur when speaking. It will also help you relay your information more concisely.

2

Speak with confidence

Speaking in a confident manner will help you build trust and command the respect of your audience.

3

Be clear and concise

Avoid using complex, convoluted sentences, and try to state your argument in direct language.

4

Be aware of your non-verbal communication signals

Pay attention to the gestures, facial expressions, and body language that you make, to ensure they align with the message you are trying to get across.

5

Be a good listener

Being a good listener will improve the quality of your verbal interactions. This enables you to build trust and rapport much more quickly.

6

Think about the perspective of your audience

Just because you have a strong command of a topic does not mean the people you are speaking to have the same knowledge. Try to think about how someone else will understand what you are trying to communicate, particularly if they lack the technical knowledge about a subject.

7

Vary your vocal tone

Speaking in a monotone voice will likely bore your audience. Instead, use voice inflection to add emphasis to important points, and vary the pitch of your voice to express emotion. This will help keep your audience engaged in your message.

11 rules for a good PowerPoint presentation

PowerPoint presentations support oral communication; they can help to systematize and organize information and deliver memorable messages, thus enabling effective communication.

1 Include only one idea per slide

Each slide should have one central message to deliver. Often, this means breaking complex ideas down into manageable pieces. You can create separate slides for each piece of information and then include a final slide with the entire diagram.

2 Spend only 1 minute per slide

When you present a slide, it should take 1 minute or less to discuss. This rule is very helpful for planning purposes: a 20-minute presentation should have somewhere around 20 slides. Also, frequently giving your audience new information helps keep them engaged. While practicing, if you find yourself spending more than one minute on a slide, there's too much information for that one slide: reduce until you get to a single message clearly described.

3 Include only one idea per slide

When each slide conveys only one message, use the heading of that slide to write exactly the message you are trying to deliver. Think of the slide heading as the introductory or concluding sentence of a paragraph.

4 Include only essential points

While you are speaking, audience members' eyes and minds will be wandering over your slide. If you have a comment, detail, or figure on a slide, have a plan to explicitly identify and talk about it. If you don't think it's important enough to spend time on, then don't have it on your slide.

5 Give credit, where credit is due

An exception to Rule 4 is to include proper citations or references to work on your slide. When adding citations, names of other researchers, or other types of credit, use a consistent style for adding this information. Your audience will then be able to easily partition this information from the other content.

6 Use graphics effectively

You should almost never have slides that only contain text. Build your slides around good visualizations. It is a visual presentation after all, a picture is worth a thousand words. However, on the other hand, don't muddy the point of the slide by using too many complex graphics. One way to ensure that you use graphics effectively is to make a point to introduce each figure and its elements to the audience verbally, especially for data figures: "This graph here shows, ...the graph demonstrates..." If you have put too much on one slide to present in 1 minute, then the complexity or number of graphics is too much for just one slide.

7 Design to avoid cognitive overload

The type and quantity of slide elements, as well as how you present them, all impact the ability of the audience to take in, organize, and remember the content. As presentations are an exercise in listening, and not reading, do what you can to optimize the ability of the audience to listen. Use words sparingly as "guideposts" to you and the audience about major points of the slide. In fact, you can add short text fragments, redundant with the verbal component of the presentation, which has been shown to improve retention. In addition to the use of short text, white space, and the effective use of graphics/images, you can further improve ease of cognitive processing by considering color choices and font type/size. Here are a few suggestions for improving the experience of your audience:

- Use high contrast colors and simple backgrounds with little to no color.
- Use sans serif fonts and large font sizes, and avoid italics or underlining (instead, use bold font for emphasis).
- Use color combinations that can be easily understood.

8 Design the slide so that a distracted person gets the main takeaway

It is very difficult to stay focused on a presentation, especially if it is long or part of a longer series of talks at a conference. It's important to look at your slide and ask, "If they heard nothing I said, will they understand the key concept of this slide?". If you are worried about not having enough details, keep a slide at the end, after your conclusions, with the more detailed information that you can refer to during a question-and-answer period.

9 Iteratively improve slide design through practice

The best way to ensure that you nailed slide design for your presentation is to practice, typically a lot. The best type of practice is in front of an audience.

The most important aspects of practicing a new presentation are the following 2 key points:

1. Practice to ensure that you hit the most important points each time through.
2. Practice to ensure that as you conclude the end of one slide, it leads directly to the next slide. Slide transitions, what you say as you end one slide and begin the next, are important for keeping the flow of the story.

10 Design to mitigate the impact of technical disasters

The real presentation almost never goes as planned. Maybe the speaker before you went over time and now you need to adjust, or some technical problem has happened. For that, you can design your slides to limit the impact of certain kinds of technical disasters by creating and preparing alternate approaches.

11 Create slides that are accessible to everyone

Creating accessible slides involves incorporating various elements to ensure inclusivity for individuals with disabilities. Start by providing clear and descriptive titles for each slide, using headings and bulleted lists to structure content, and adding alternative text to images for screen reader users. Maintain high contrast between text and background, avoiding reliance on color alone to convey information. Opt for accessible fonts and font sizes, and include closed captions for videos and text transcripts for audio content. Avoid automatic slide advancement or provide control options, and test the presentation for accessibility using built-in features and screen reader software. Additionally, consider providing navigation shortcuts and a table of contents for easy maneuverability. By implementing these strategies, you can create presentations that cater to a diverse audience and ensure that information is accessible to all.

3.5- Video-making

In the following section, you can find some guidelines to make great videos for the internet. Videos are a great way to spread a message because they make a message easier to remember. The attention span of a human being is just 8 seconds, so it is very important to catch the viewers' attention!

How to correctly structure a message

A well-structured message has three parts: an introduction, ideas, and a conclusion. This is mostly universal, and there is something humanly digestible about it. This concept is visible in the world of marketing: "three ways our product can help you," "three ways our product works...", etc. In theatre, there is an opening act, where the characters and the scenarios are set, the second act, where the drama and conflict happen, and the final act, where there is a resolution. More than three parts usually gets confusing and more difficult to remember, and you want to be clear and straightforward.

1. INTRODUCTION: It is very important because it is where you must catch our viewers' attention. People do not usually give away their time, so if someone opens your video, it is your duty to make them stay. Wake them to develop their curiosity.

There are three questions people usually ask themselves about things: **what, how, and why.** What are they, how do they work, and why it can interest me?

Example: You want to speak about plant-based diets and protein intake. You are already a vegetarian, and you know that you can get all the protein you need from plants, but the person watching you might not know that. So, you can tell them something like...

"Protein is one of the most important nutrients, and there's a misconception that you can't obtain protein from plants. But that's not true, find out how to achieve this!" You see? There's a hook there, you've got to work on that hook!

2. DEVELOP YOUR IDEAS: Three ideas are a good amount, because just one idea is too weak and too many ideas are too much information. It's important to find and summarize a few ideas of what we are trying to communicate.

Example: You are trying to argue that Lord of the Rings is the best fantasy movie. If you say, "it's the best because there are elves, dragons, or whatever..." it just feels weak. However, you could say that there is an epic battle between good and evil, there's a history of impossible love, and that even the most unimportant person can change the history. That's a better argument, isn't it?

3. CONCLUSION: Ask yourself what you want to stick in the minds of people that listened to you. There is an opportunity here; they listened all the way to the end, so they are interested.

Do not just finish the video, you have the power now, so you should:

- Make an **outline** of the ideas you shared.
- Include a **CTA (Call to Action)**: It is the time to ask the viewer to do something. You can also ask them to comment on your video, which is going to give you more visibility and better engagement with your audience. Don't just ask for a general opinion, ask easy questions because people love to talk about themselves.

More ideas to include in your video:

- Add graphics: Add graphs, charts, or images to support what you're saying.
- Use humour if possible: It's always important to keep your content fun.
- Tell personal stories: Tell a personal story about yourself if its relevant, people love stories.
- Add quotes: Add a relevant quote from someone respected, as it validates what you're saying, shows respect, and gives your idea another point of view.

Example: If you're going make videos about farming, talk about how your grandparents used to make the things you're showing.

Include a good title

Finally, think of a good title! It is less important on social media, but very important, for example, on YouTube. There are two wrong ways to write a title:

1. **CLICKBAIT:** you see a title that says something so stupid that you must click on it. This is unwise because when you trick someone into watching, they will be disappointed when you don't deliver the expected content.
2. **ANTI-CLICKBAIT:** you are so anti-clickbait that you make the most boring title in the world. This means zero views.

There's a middle ground between these approaches, and it may be helpful to look at what newspaper editors have been writing.

Video applications

There are free applications available to create videos on your mobile phone:

- [Adobe Premiere Rush](#)
- [CapCut](#)
- [Filmora](#)

[Here are some examples of the COCOREADO Ambassadors' Videos!](#)

3.6- Podcasting

Podcasting as a communication tool

Over the past 10 years, the number of weekly podcast listeners has risen every year. For example, 35% of Spanish internet users will now listen to at least one podcast episode per week. The rise in popularity is partly due to the unique nature of podcasts – you can find a specific podcast on almost any topic. The beauty of podcasting is letting listeners choose a niche topic that is specific to their interests. This creates a unique opportunity for campaigners to create a communication tool that targets a niche audience.

Podcasts are intimate. They give you the opportunity to dive deep into a topic and communicate the complex nature of a certain subject, that simply can't be communicated via fast-paced social media platforms.

Several of the COCOREADO partner organisations have their own podcasts to disseminate their information to members, partners, and the general public. For example:

- [Rural Voices – the Rural Youth Europe Podcast](#)
- [MIJARC Europe – The Interview Series](#)
- [CEJA – FARMRes podcast on mental health](#)

Getting started

- **Choose your niche and target audience:** Think about who you want to listen to the podcast. Is it the general public? Is it policy makers? You need to have the target audience in mind before you plan any content.
- **Write a plan:** What structure will use? Will it be interview based? A solo speaker sharing their views? Or a panel discussion between a group of individuals? Work out the beginning, middle, and end of the episode so you have a plan before you get behind the microphone.
- **Practise recording:** You don't need a fancy microphone to get started – the microphone on your phone is good enough to get going. Practise recording yourself and practise interviewing people on the topic.
- **Don't make it too long:** research has shown that 22 minutes is the optimal listening time. After 22 minutes, listening figures tend to drop off.
- **The edit:** Once you've recorded your audio, you can edit it using free online software (Audacity, GarageBand). Add some music at the start and end, and record an intro and outro to make it sound more professional.
- **Share it:** You can upload to Spotify and Apple Podcasts via a podcast host platform. Buzzsprout is a great hosting platform, but you can create a free account on SoundCloud to quickly get your content accessible.
- **Promote on social media:** Recording a podcast gives you lots of content. Think about how you could use this content in other ways, such as Reels on Instagram or TikToks. Interviews can also be transcribed to form blog posts for your website. If you want to target policy makers, perhaps think about sharing a clip of your podcast on LinkedIn.

Interview tips

- LISTEN! If the interviewee says something interesting, don't be afraid to ask more. You may not have prepared a certain question or topic, but if you think you can find something interesting in the moment, don't be afraid to go down a different avenue of discussion.
- Have a beginning, middle, and end planned. But make sure to let the conversation flow in an informal and relaxed way. The charm of a podcast is that it feels like you are eavesdropping on a conversation.
- Have a few key questions prepared just in case you lose track of the conversation and want to bring it back to the topic.
- Don't interrogate - keep it informal and conversational.
- Show your passion for the subject. Enthusiasm is infectious - show your energy for the topic in your voice.

[Example: Listen to the COCOREADO Riga podcast episode here.](#)

This podcast episode is co-hosted by the ambassadors, and they talk about how they are 'campaigning for change' in the context of the COCOREADO project. Hear more about the ambassadors, what they've learnt from the training, the power of campaigning and the strength of the COCOREADO network.

COCOREADO H2020 PROJECT

FOOD SYSTEM INNOVATOR TOOLKIT

CH4 Engaging with Policy

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- 3 Guidelines to approach local policymakers
- 4 Dissemination channels and European networks
- 5 A practical example: Urban food policy and ways of engaging with it

4.1- Introduction

In this section of the Toolkit, we will focus on policies related to food and farming systems, and how it is possible to interact with them in a bottom-up manner from an individual, group, or organisational level.

Engaging with policy can lead to impact at different levels: local, national, as well as European.

Policy cycles are an integral part of any policy development.

These cycles include:

- Agenda Setting
- Policy Formulation
- Adoption
- Implementation
- Evaluation
- Maintenance

The following chapter explores ways that the agenda setting phase can be influenced from a bottom-up perspective.

Here you will find information on how to:

- Establish policy-oriented communication
- Produce a policy brief
- Prepare a policy workshop
- Address and engage with a local urban food policy

Achieving shifts in policies regulating food can be the most effective way to ensure that food systems change. Collaborative activities bridging the gaps between activists, entrepreneurs, and policymakers can result in food strategies, focused policies, and new procurement arrangements that lead to more responsible food systems.

4.2- Policy-oriented communication

How to prepare a policy campaign

This section will delve into the world of policy-oriented communication, which requires a distinct approach. Just like in business, effective communication plays a pivotal role in policy formulation, implementation, and evaluation. Nonetheless, it requires a specific understanding of the government structure and legislative timeline to be effective. Let's explore how to prepare a campaign for change in the context of policy-oriented communication.

Establishing Policy Communication Goals

In the realm of policy, defining communication goals is a crucial step in shaping the course of your campaign. Why is communication important? What are the policy objectives you seek to attain? These fundamental questions should steer the development of your communication goals. Much like in the business world, policy communication objectives should adhere to **the SMART criteria**:

SPECIFIC

What legislative or administrative changes are you striving for, and do they fall within the jurisdiction of the entity you are addressing?

In the multi-layered governance system of the European Union, not every level possesses the authority to enact legislation on all issues. For instance, in matters related to agriculture and rural areas, certain competences are exclusive to the EU, while others are shared with national or regional levels of member states. The EU holds exclusive competences in areas related to the single market^[1], whereas agricultural legislation is typically a shared competence, ideally applied at the most effective governance level under the subsidiarity^[2] principle.

- Identify the specific legislative or administrative changes you're advocating for.
- Determine if these changes fall within the jurisdiction of the entity you're addressing.
- Ensure clarity on whether the issue is within the exclusive competence of the EU, shared with member states, or at a regional level.
- Consider whether your proposed changes align with the subsidiarity principle.

[1] The European single market is comprising the 27 member states of the European Union (EU). Some third countries also have a privileged access to the single market: Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway (through the Agreement on the European Economic Area), and Switzerland (through sectoral treaties). The single market seeks to guarantee the free movement of goods, capital, services, and people. This is achieved through common rules and standards that all participating states are legally committed to follow.

[2] Subsidiarity is a principle of social organization that holds that social and political issues should be dealt with at the most immediate or local level that is consistent with their resolution.

MEASURABLE

- Define clear goals regarding alterations to government budgets or policies.
- Assess the potential consequences of these changes, particularly in terms of budgetary implications and sector sustainability.
- Determine how you will track progress towards your goals.
- Consider the multi-annual framework of EU budgets, and the challenges associated with securing substantial budget increases within a short timeline.

ACHIEVABLE

Are you operating within the window of opportunity to advocate for your desired change?

Based on your research, to make your campaign objectives specific to the legislation, relevant to the policymakers involved, and within the budgetary scope of the targeted legislation, it's advisable to ensure they are realistically attainable within a defined timeframe.

- Evaluate the current window of opportunity for advocating your desired change (ongoing policy evaluation, media coverage of the topic, etc.).
- Ensure that your objectives are realistically attainable within a defined timeframe.
- Ensure that your objectives are achievable within the mandate of the relevant policymaker.
- Consider the political climate and the feasibility of achieving your goals given the current context.

RELEVANT

Is your objective aligned with your long-term goals, and does it align with the current political agenda?

This assessment will determine your ability to rally supporters within your window of opportunity. To build a coalition around your objectives, it's essential to ascertain whether your issue is already on the policymaking agenda or if it can be added to the agenda. Unless you hold policymaking authority, you must collaborate with an ally who possesses the influence to set the agenda.

- Align your objectives with your long-term goals and overall agenda.
- Assess whether your objectives are aligned with the current political agenda.
- Determine if your issue is already on the policymaking agenda or if it can be added.
- Identify potential allies or coalitions that can support your objectives and help influence the policymaking agenda.

TIME-BOUND

Have the legislative processes already commenced?

Once you've determined the relevance of your proposed legislation, you must consider whether any existing legislation on the subject requires updating. Advocating for a policy change when the current policymaking cycle is near completion and implementation has begun is typically too late. The window of opportunity may have closed, necessitating a wait until the next maintenance phase to bring the topic back onto the policy agenda.

- Determine if legislative processes relevant to your objectives have already commenced.
- Assess whether existing legislation on the subject requires updating.
- Avoid advocating for changes too late in the policymaking cycle when implementation has already begun.
- Consider the timing of your advocacy efforts in relation to policy maintenance phases and agenda-setting opportunities.

Following these steps will ensure that your resources are allocated efficiently to achieve these objectives:

1. Identifying Target Stakeholder Groups

In policy-oriented communication, it's crucial to identify and engage various stakeholder groups, such as government agencies, interest groups (e.g. trade unions, environmental NGOs, industry groups, academic institutions), media, and the public. These groups need to be clearly defined, considering their roles and interests. The selection of channels and the tone of your communication should align with the diverse needs and expectations of these stakeholders if you want them to act on your demands and become your allies towards policy change.

2. Crafting Policy Messages

Policy messages must be well-crafted, reflecting the values of your organization or your endeavour, and addressing the concerns of your audience. These messages should be clear and precise, using language and tone appropriate for your target audience. It should not be too complex or long. In policy communication, the goal is not just to sell a product, but to persuade and inform stakeholders and policymakers about the importance and implications of the policy. In your communication you should convey your understanding of policymaking and be timely with your messages. For instance, it's important to send your arguments ahead of the final debate in the plenary session of the parliament; your messages should have already been received by the members of Parliament sitting in topic specific committees. For the European Parliament, you can follow the legislative agenda via the Legislative Train Schedule^[3].

3. Choosing Communication Channels and Formulating an Action Plan

Just as in business, the choice of communication channels is essential in policy-oriented communication. Channels may include press releases, public forums, government briefings, reports, and social media, but also more privileged channels such as bilateral calls or meetings if you manage to get access. Your action plan should outline the objectives of each communication action, the platforms you'll use, and the timing of these actions. The selection of channels should be based on where policymakers and your audience are most likely to be informed and engaged.

4. Timing and Frequency in Policy Communication

Policy communication must be strategic in terms of timing and frequency. Sending out messages randomly or too frequently can lead to stakeholder fatigue and reduced effectiveness. Ensure that the timing and frequency of communication aligns with your policy goals and the specific needs of different stakeholder groups. In the policy cycle, ideal moments to advocate for change are typically between agenda setting and policy formulation (for the EU, use the Have your say platform^[4]), and during policy maintenance phases for policies that have already been adopted (participate in evaluation surveys, read evaluation reports, and contact the relevant services with the power of legislative initiative). Pick your battles! Policy change is a long process, and you don't want to run out of resources after the first debate in committee.

5. Continuous Improvement in Policy Communication

As with business communication, policy communication campaigns should be measurable. Depending on the nature of your policy and the objectives set, these evaluations may be weekly, monthly, or quarterly. Continual improvement is crucial in the dynamic field of policy to adapt and refine your approach.

[3] [Legislative Train Schedule \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say_en)

[4] https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say_en

A concrete illustration

Let's consider a concrete example of young farmers in the European Union (EU) trying to secure more funding under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The CAP is a crucial policy framework that governs agricultural subsidies, rural development, and environmental programs in the EU.

1

Establishing Policy Communication Goals

In this case, the young farmers' communication goals are to advocate for specific changes in the CAP legislation, aimed at securing increased funding and support for their generation. Their objectives should align with the SMART criteria:

SPECIFIC: The young farmers are seeking legislative changes in the CAP that provide more targeted and substantial financial assistance for young farmers, thereby ensuring the sustainability and growth of their agricultural businesses. They need to work within the framework of the EU's shared competence in agricultural legislation and the subsidiarity principle.

MEASURABLE: Their campaign should focus on quantifiable objectives, such as a percentage increase in financial support for young farmers. They should also emphasize the potential positive impact of these changes on the agricultural sector's sustainability and youth employment.

ACHIEVABLE: The campaign should target a legislative window where the EU is discussing CAP reforms. To ensure achievability, the young farmers should conduct thorough research on the ongoing legislative discussions and identify key decision-makers within the EU institutions.

RELEVANT: Their objective should align with their long-term goals of making agriculture an attractive career choice for young people, and it should align with the current political agenda regarding agricultural and rural development policies in the EU.

TIME-BOUND: The legislative processes related to CAP are cyclical. The young farmers must ensure that their campaign is launched well in advance of the next CAP reform discussions to maximize their chances of influencing the outcome.

2

Identifying target stakeholder groups

The young farmers must identify and engage various stakeholder groups in their campaign:

- **European Commission:** As the institution responsible for CAP proposals, they should target relevant Directorates-General, Units, and Commissioners.
- **Members of the European Parliament (MEPs):** Engaging with MEPs who sit on the Agriculture and Rural Development Committee is essential.
- **National Agriculture Ministries:** Cooperation with national governments, particularly their agriculture ministries, is crucial.
- **Farmers' Associations:** Collaborating with existing farmers' associations and rural development organizations to amplify their message.
- **Youth Organizations:** Partnering with youth organizations to highlight the importance of supporting young farmers.

3

Crafting policy messages

The young farmers' policy messages should:

- **Highlight the Importance:** Emphasize the significance of young farmers in ensuring the future of agriculture and the revitalization of rural areas.
- **Quantify Impact:** Use data and case studies to demonstrate the positive impact of increased funding on employment, rural development, and food security.
- **Appeal to Values:** Frame their campaign around values such as sustainability, generational renewal, and the economic wellbeing of rural communities.
- **Be Timely:** Ensure their messages are delivered well in advance of CAP reform debates.

4

Choosing Communication Channels and Formulating an Action Plan

The young farmers can use various communication channels:

- **Press Releases:** Announce their campaign's launch and key milestones.
- **Social Media:** Utilize platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram to engage the public and policymakers.
- **Meetings:** Arrange meetings with MEPs, Commission officials, and national agriculture ministers.
- **Public Forums:** Organize public events and forums to raise awareness.
- **Reports:** Publish reports showcasing their research findings and policy recommendations

Their action plan should include a timeline with key milestones, such as releasing a policy proposal, organizing a public rally, and submitting their recommendations to relevant EU institutions.

5

Timing and frequency in policy communication

The young farmers must strategically time their communications, especially in alignment with the CAP reform cycle. Regular but not excessive updates should be delivered to keep stakeholders informed without causing fatigue.

6

Continuous improvement in policy communication

The young farmers should continually evaluate the impact of their campaign, make necessary adjustments, and adapt to changing circumstances. This includes measuring the engagement levels on social media, tracking media coverage, and assessing the reception of their policy recommendations by policymakers.

By following these strategies and principles, young farmers can effectively prepare a policy-oriented communication campaign to advocate for more funding in the CAP, ultimately ensuring a brighter future for agriculture in the EU and supporting the next generation of farmers.

How to produce a policy brief

According to the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO)[5], a policy brief is a **concise summary of a particular issue, the policy options to deal with it, and some recommendations on the best options**. It is aimed at government policymakers and others who are interested in formulating or influencing policy, and its added value remains in the explanation of the urgency of that particular issue, focusing on presenting findings and providing achievable recommendations.

Bearing in mind that it is written for certain audiences, in this case policymakers, there are some **fundamental requirements** to be taken into consideration before producing a policy brief:

- Short document with a clear purpose
- Presents the problem/challenge and recommendations
- Evidence-based
- Represents the standpoint of a whole organization

Having a clear purpose

The policy brief must be a well-written document, so the target audience fully understands its purpose. It is a recommendation document, so in order to maximize the success of the presented recommendation, the underlying issue must be well highlighted and clearly explained. It should be possible to clearly identify the constraints created by the issue, even if the reader is not an expert in the general subject presented.

Presents the problem/challenge and recommendations

The core of this document is made up of two topics: the problems and the recommendations. The purpose of a policy brief is to highlight pressing problems in a given area and present recommendations for solving them. The document should be developed around these objectives, ideally supported by real examples and evidence, and written in a straightforward way so the impact of the problems and suggested recommendations can be easily recognised.

Evidence-based

A policy brief shouldn't be confused with opinion content or a summary of scientific research. Nevertheless, it increases credibility in the eyes of readers if it includes some research-based evidence, particularly if readers are unfamiliar with the presented issues.

Represents the standpoint of the whole entity

Naturally, such an important document should represent the viewpoint of an entire entity (i.e. any group of people with similar interests who have decided to collaborate on producing the document). In this case, if a potential recommendation is questioned within the group, those doubts should not show through in the document, since it is supposed to present a single well-directed viewpoint. It is not meant to be an open-ended document, as differing interpretations could cause doubt in the implementation of certain recommendations. The purpose and benefits of a recommendation for a particular issue could be unclear if the recommendation itself is also unclear.

With these considerations in mind, the process of producing a policy brief reflects the following steps:

[5] The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) is a specialized agency of the United Nations that leads international efforts to defeat hunger. Our goal is to achieve food security for all and make sure that people have regular access to enough high-quality food to lead active, healthy lives.

STARTING POINT:

- Define the debate you want to participate in.
- Is the idea timely? Is there a debate going on?
- Does your idea add value to the debate?

PREPARATIONS:

Identify:

- What is the specific challenge or problem that requires policymakers' attention?
- What specific recommendations do you want to give to the policymakers?

Discuss, agree, and write down:

- Purpose: Why are you writing this policy brief?
- Key message: Briefly, what do you want to say to the policymakers?
- The audience: To whom are you writing?

CHALLENGES / PROBLEMS:

- What is the challenge/problem faced in the real world?
- How is it manifested in practice?
- How do you illustrate that the challenge is in the scope of your project/organization?

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Give recommendations to solve/relieve the problem/challenge described.

Use clear statements with concrete advice.

For example, ask:

- What is the core idea of the recommendation?
- In what circumstances/environments/situations is the recommendation feasible?
- Are there alternative recommendations for different situations?
- Who benefits if the recommendation is implemented?

WRITING:

A policy brief is written to policymakers who are not necessarily specialists in the area, and have very limited time to focus on your policy brief. So:

- Write in clear, jargon-free language.
- Be brief!
- Make it visually attractive.

Every policy brief is unique. Select a structure and layout that highlights your core message. The following elements should be found in the policy brief: Title, summary, introduction, challenges/problems, recommendations, introduction of the releasing organization/project.

TITLE AND SUMMARY:

- What are the main points you want policymakers to understand, even if they read nothing else?
- The title and the summary are the first things a reader sees; they should lure in the reader to read the whole policy brief.

INTRODUCTION:

- Highlights the urgency of the policy brief.
- Ties the policy brief to ongoing debate, EU initiatives for example.

CHALLENGES/PROBLEMS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- Select the best way to introduce the challenges/problems and recommendations.
- Be precise with your recommendations!

RELEASING ORGANIZATION/PROJECT, AUTHORS, AND REFERENCES:

- A very brief introduction on releasing organization/project.
- Authors are listed if they can provide additional knowledge on the topic.
- References should be used cautiously, focusing on sources connected directly to the policy brief

SHARING THE POLICY BRIEF WITH THE AUDIENCE: HOW TO REACH THE POLICYMAKERS?

- Use every measure necessary.
- Extract the key recommendations and use them in social media.
- Use personal networks to reach the key audience.

[Check examples of policy briefs produced by COCOREADO here!](#)

1. Lowering the barriers for farmers to participate in sustainable public procurement
2. Empowering Young Citizens Involvement in Transition Towards Sustainable Food Systems
3. Benefiting from new business opportunities require business skills

4.3- Guidelines to approach local policymakers

Identifying and engaging with the most relevant policy makers

Given the possible complexity of different policy decision-making systems at the regional, national, and EU level, before identifying responsible policy makers and contacting them, the first step should be gaining knowledge on how the system works, where the decisions are taking place, and who are responsible persons. Once you have this understanding, you can proceed with developing a strategy for approaching the policymakers and think about possible instruments to do this.

The next consequent step would be to **identify the most relevant policymakers**. These may not necessarily be the ones with the most decision power, but those who are more likely to understand your statements and recommendations. Even though there is no one way to precisely spot the right policymaker, it might be helpful to identify which policymaker talks publicly (or has written reports, given interviews, etc.) on topics close to the issues that you want to raise.

If the policy brief is more tailored to the interests of particular policymakers, they might feel more part of the process and drive more lobbying within the environment of policy decision-makers. This way, there will be a higher potential of achieving the objective.

When it comes to identifying the most relevant policymakers, the starting point should be defining the scope of the target, whether it's at the **local, regional, national, or European level**. Only after clearly defining this target should you proceed to map out which institutions and/or individual policymakers to approach.

The starting point of the process can often seem somewhat challenging, either because of the inherent complexity of the decision-making system (which can complicate understanding of which specific institutions and policymakers have decision-making power), or due to a lack of knowledge of direct contacts that should be approached in order to identify the most relevant policymakers.

A possible solution could be to deconstruct the steps, establishing stages to identify the most relevant policymakers for your purpose. Identifying contacts in stages could lead to greater success in identifying the ideal policymakers, so that it is possible to adjust your method of reaching out and communicating with the target audience.

Adjusting your method of reaching out and communicating with the target audience

For example, if you have decided to approach local policy offices, it may be easier to present supporting documentation such as a leaflet with policy recommendations. Additionally, it is important to be assertive in setting up an interaction with local decision-makers, as the communication streams are simpler and the level of discussion allows a better understanding of the urgent needs and subsequent proposed policy recommendations.

On the other hand, given an example where the aim is to reach a policymaker at the European level, organisations within the EU decision-making system that produce policies and advise decision-makers in specific fields of action should be identified. After that, the organisation's stakeholders should be identified and advised on your policy recommendations. This can be ensured through **direct contact with a policymaker, by promoting a campaign**, or extending it to the organisation of an event where the information can reach multiple actors simultaneously, such as **a policy workshop**.

Policy workshop preparation

Policy workshops are events where you can promote the dissemination of policy recommendations to decision-makers. Firstly, you need to **clearly define the goals and objectives of the workshop as well as identify the most suitable audience for the event**. You can also choose relevant policymakers to invite based on the policy recommendations you want to present.

The right audience is essential for organising such an event, as policy is a specific subject that needs at least a minimum level of background knowledge to achieve productive debates and ensure that policy recommendations are framed within the normal set-up for policy offices. For example, organising an event for an audience of people unfamiliar with the framework of policy briefs can make it difficult to present the content of a developed policy brief. Alternately, organising a policy workshop for an audience of people unfamiliar with the framework of policy briefs could also provide some valuable insights, such as adjusting the layout of the policy brief since it is desirable that it is easy to read and understand.

Then, after defining the right target audience, it must be decided **whether to organise the event in person or online**. Clearly, online events are currently very popular due to the comfort and ease of accessibility for participants, but there are certain topics that require a face-to-face event where interactive sessions, as "World Café", "I Couldn't Disagree More" and others, can be promoted.

It's essential to gather as much feedback as possible at these events, so you can take the various feedback into account to adjust your message to the needs of the decision-makers, so your recommendations are more likely to be put into practice in the future.

Additionally, the **presence of speakers representing political offices at the EU level should be mandatory**, not only to promote the credibility of an event, but also to bring other organisations together and encourage greater interest in attending.

Once all these requirements have been defined, the technical preparations for the event must begin, keeping the following points in mind:

- Preparing invitations for the participants, where it should be clear what the aim of the event is, what the expected outcomes are, and how they will be used.
- Date and location (if not online)
- Agenda
- Guest speakers
- Event promotion and participants

Date and Location

The date of the event should be the first thing decided, even if it is subject to change afterwards due to unforeseen circumstances, such as unavailability of venues or unavailability of a participant who is crucial to the event. Thus, to minimise any possible date changes, the event should be planned at least 3 months in advance (if it is to be held in person), and a time window of 1 week can be set if the initial date for the event has to be changed.

After deciding whether it will be an online or face-to-face seminar, it's time to decide on the venue. To ensure that the target audience can participate without any constraints, accessibility must be highly considered, as well as the size and layout of the venue, considering the expected number of participants and additional technical equipment.

Agenda and Guest speakers

The agenda is essential not only to ensure that the event runs smoothly, but also to captivate the audience. The event can be held for part of the day (morning or afternoon) or all day depending on the type of event, although a 3-hour event may prove very productive if it is well planned.

To engage the target audience, it is recommended that the agenda includes the names of the guest speakers, so it's necessary to confirm the presence of the guest speakers in advance. In the case of a policy workshop, it's recommended that the guest speakers are individuals representing policy offices at the EU level, due to their relevance to the topic and the audience they attract through their presence at the event.

Regarding the sessions, about 15 minutes should be allocated at the beginning for a brief introduction to the event and its context. If the number of participants enables it, a brief icebreaker activity can facilitate communication and encourage individuals to feel more comfortable in a group.

Throughout the event, ideally, there should be a combination of lecture sessions focused on introducing the topics for discussion, and debate sessions. Give priority to the latter, so participants can elaborate on the content presented and generate productive debates. Remember, it's also essential to include short, frequent breaks to keep participants energised.

Event Promotion and Participants

As described previously, identifying the most suitable audience is one of the main requirements for organising an event of this kind. After this process, the next step is to prepare and send invitations to the defined list of target participants.

When sending out event invitations, it's important to ensure that participants have enough time to organise themselves before registration closes, which requires carefully planned dissemination of the event.

The event can be promoted in 3 phases: a **save the date** 3 months before the event, an **invitation** 2 months before the event, and a **reminder** 1 month before the event. This can be shared through the same channels used to invite the participants, or through flyers, if justifiable. Contacts can be made directly with potential workshop participants and then invitations sent out as soon as they confirm their participation or the invitations can be made using various means of communication, such as social media platforms or more broadly inviting emails.

Follow up on the event

After the workshop event, it is important to ensure that the participants felt that the event created added value to the main topics discussed. It's also essential to ensure that the ideas and recommendations presented and discussed were meaningful, and that the event participants will be disseminating them to other relevant stakeholders.

This follow-up could already be encouraged at the end of the event by inviting participants to collaborate in sharing supporting educational material related to your goals.

4.4- Dissemination channels and European networks

Nowadays, there are several active networks with a focus on agricultural and rural areas, such as: EU CAP Network, Youth organizations networks (RYE, CEJA, MIJARC), National CAP Networks. These networks are connected between themselves, in order to promote a valuable flow of information. The exchange of ideas has never been so easy and user friendly as it is now, and this should be taken advantage of.

There are simple ways to disseminate the information, such as various social media platforms, where it is possible to promote dissemination on different platforms, with different audiences and contexts, and as varied networks.

As for networks, each type of network must be considered, from personal networks to broader networks. Elaborating on this, and given a COCOREADO project example, we can either **approach our closest circles** regarding sustainable food consumption, or we can approach **wider consumers' networks and other farmers' networks** active in food education issues that promote training and dissemination of good practices to ensure awareness of sustainable food consumption. Additionally, we could approach an identical consumer network active in another region and identify possible synergies in order to strengthen the exchange of information and the implementation of good practices.

Ultimately, the approach to European networks that have close linkages to policy offices which produce policies and advise policymakers would be ideal, in the sense that the more we promote contact with networks of increasing size, the closer we will be to informing decision-makers of the issues and recommendations we intend to advocate for.

4.5- A practical example: urban food policy and ways of engaging with it

Urban food policies encompass not only food consumption, but ideally also production and the connection between both ends of the supply chain. However, developing a food policy is something a lot of cities struggle with. Therefore, collaborating with local governments and engaging with the urban food policy at any development stage is a way to inspire action towards more sustainable and just food systems for the citizens of the city.

Why urban food policy?

To date, hundreds of cities have developed policies and programs on urban food security, nutrition, urban agriculture, and similar topics, often in collaboration with civil society and private sector stakeholders in the food system[6]. These policies and programs vary widely in scope, ranging from single-issue plans that address specific elements of the food system (e.g., food waste reduction plans), to comprehensive approaches that assess and plan the urban (or city-region) agri-food system[7] or provide vulnerable social groups like unemployed people, families with many children, or retired people with access to urban or peri-urban areas where they can grow their food. This diversity results in different food-related initiatives originating from both private and public sectors, as well as civil society. However, a lot of these initiatives lack a central focus and vision to build upon for long-term changes at the city level. To align various food efforts in a city and to approach the food system of a city holistically, urban food strategies (UFSs) are being developed. In essence, a UFS is a plan and process to inspire action towards more sustainable and just food systems for all – a working document that needs to be updated regularly, serving as a starting point rather than an end goal[8].

Possible challenges when striving for a sustainable food system in the city

City councils play a crucial role in promoting positive change within their cities and influencing the evolution of the food system. It can be accomplished in different ways, for instance by:

- Establishing legislation and regulation frameworks
- Offering incentives through funding
- Initiating the creation of city food councils
- Creating public food procurement plans
- Fostering connections among different actors of the food chain.

Opportunities for change can be found in areas such as catering contracts, where the focus can be on offering more vegetarian or organic options and collaborating with small and medium-sized enterprises. Additionally, spatial policy and improving access to healthy food are vital aspects where cities can make meaningful contributions through, for example, the creation of urban allotment gardens.

Despite the possibilities for positive change, cities also face certain limitations when striving for a sustainable food system, and it is crucial to be aware of these challenges during the development of a UFS. Some of the challenges that cities encounter include:

- **Cities and municipalities face limitations as their jurisdiction is limited to their own territory.** Often, agricultural areas lie outside the cities, in neighbouring villages, forming the green belt around the city. In these villages, the cities lack jurisdiction, making collaboration with the neighbouring villages essential when cities want to engage in buying local produce or working with local farmers. However, this collaboration can be challenging due to local politics and other factors.

[6] Zeeuw, H. de, & Drechsel, P. (2015). *Cities and Agriculture: Developing Resilient Urban Food Systems*. Routledge.

[7] Smaal, S. A. L., Dessein, J., Wind, B. J., & Rogge, E. (2021). Social justice-oriented narratives in European urban food strategies: Bringing forward redistribution, recognition and representation. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 38(3), 709–727.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-020-10179-6>

[8] Moragues, A., Morgan, K., Moschitz, H., Neimane, I., Nilsson, H., Pinto, M., Rohrer, H., Ruiz, R., Thuswald, M., Tisenkops, T., & Halliday, J. (2013). *Urban Food Strategies: The rough guide to sustainable food systems*.

- **Smaller cities and towns may lack capacity to develop a comprehensive UFS on their own.** To successfully build bridges between different policy domains and initiatives, there is a need for a paid worker with expertise in the field. This individual can facilitate coordination and cooperation among various stakeholders effectively.
- **Urban food policies encompass multiple policy domains and do not have a domain of their own.** Instead, they intersect with various areas, such as land-use planning, infrastructure and transport, environmental conservation, housing, and economic development. Although food can potentially serve as a vehicle to integrate these domains, the practical integration of different policy areas proves challenging.
- Finally, local and national policymakers may simply **not be familiar with the notion of urban agriculture** and cannot acknowledge the benefits that it can provide for cities and citizens. In these cases, there is a lot of room for engaging with policy change from a bottom-up level.

Some additional challenges commonly faced when developing a UFS, whether through top-down or bottom-up approaches, are as follows:

- **Lack of political support.** Urban food strategies may not always receive sufficient political support, especially when they are developed from the bottom-up by community stakeholders. This lack of support can hinder effective implementation of the strategy.
- **Insufficient budget allocation:** Despite initial enthusiasm and widespread interest in participating, many UFSs suffer from a lack of adequate funding. This budget constraint often arises due to the multifaceted nature of food policies spread across different domains.
- **Limited implementation of tools:** Without adequate tools, it becomes challenging to transform the vision into concrete actions.
- **Limited involvement of farmers:** In some cases, farmers and urban gardeners may not be actively engaged or adequately represented in the development of UFS (although farmer unions often are). This limited involvement can result in a lack of perspective from key stakeholders in the food system, impacting the strategy's effectiveness and sustainability.

To effectively address these challenges, the UFS must be developed in a participatory and inclusive manner, involving all relevant stakeholders. Key actors such as policymakers from different domains, farmers, gardeners, researchers, entrepreneurs, environmental organisations, agricultural organisations, health and educational organisations, and citizens should be actively engaged in the process [9]. Their collaboration is vital to ensure the envisioned transition in urban food systems is robust enough to tackle a variety of upcoming challenges.

Engaging these different actors is crucial when tackling city-level challenges. This can be achieved through the creation of a food council, steering committee, or food partnership. Moreover, the level of engagement in these groups may vary from city to city, with some individuals participating more actively than others. While compensation for participation may sometimes be provided, it is not always a prerequisite for involvement in these initiatives. For instance, the development of an urban garden may be a voluntary endeavour, especially when it is started from bottom-up efforts, which should be taken into consideration.

For more inspiration, you can find examples of three urban food strategies in the annex of this chapter.

[9] Moragues, A., Morgan, K., Moschitz, H., Neimane, I., Nilsson, H., Pinto, M., Rohrer, H., Ruiz, R., Thuswald, M., Tisenkops, T., & Halliday, J. (2013). *Urban Food Strategies: The rough guide to sustainable food systems*.

Ways of engaging with your local urban food policy

Your way of engaging with the urban food policy and developing urban food strategy will depend on both the state of readiness of the city and your role in the food system. While in some cases the most convenient options might be either explaining your vision or suggestions in a written form or meeting face to-face with one or a small group of representatives of the municipality, we also suggest trying out the workshop method.

During the COCOREADO programme, a workshop was held to help to develop the urban food strategy of Riga by gathering together representatives of the Riga City Council and young people who are enthusiastic about changing the food system from across Europe. During the workshop, the **PlayDecide Tool** was used to define the main aspects that should be considered when developing the urban food strategy of Riga.

The PlayDecide card game[10] was launched in 2004 as part of the EU-funded project Decide (2004-2007). It allows for a simple, respectful, and fact-based group discussion. It facilitates an inclusive dialogue, allowing diverse perspectives to be heard and fostering consensus building among stakeholders. Using this game, the players can get familiar with the topic; it will help them to see different perspectives, and form their own opinion. As a group they look at an issue and try to reach a positive consensus about the proposed policy positions.

The game consists of different types of cards that can be played out during several rounds to gain varying perspectives on food policy and the issues it should encompass. The types of cards include:

Story Card 4

Sam, Netherlands

Last year I joined a community-supported agriculture project. They connected us with a local farmer and we pay €15 a week for a seasonal selection of fruit and veg that they deliver to my place! The neighbours all come and pick up their bag. It's hard to imagine this could work on a big scale and it's true that in winter, we end up with a lot of cabbage - I'm not sure I'm getting all my nutrients there! But there's a real feeling of solidarity and it's connected me with my neighbours.

- **Story cards** which feature personas related to the food system. They allow participants choose those participants of the food supply chain and corresponding story cards that they find relevant for the discussion. While picking the story cards, they consider if these types of personas should be actively involved in the development of an urban food strategy.

Figure 1. Example of a story card of PlayDecide

[10] <https://playdecide.eu/>

- **Info cards** which present information on various food-related topics. Participants can choose topics that should be involved in the development of an urban food strategy.

Figure 2. Example of an info card of PlayDecide

- **Issue cards** that highlight different challenges and problems related to the food system. They allow meaningful conversations and brainstorming sessions aimed at understanding the complexities of the food system.

Figure 3. Example of an issue card of PlayDecide

Working with the different types of cards and clustering them around central themes and topics, and defining corresponding policy positions (i.e. themes and the topics that policymakers should be considering), is a structured and productive way to reach consensus on the ideas that are important for developing a new urban food strategy. Alternatively, they can also be used to gain inspiration for upgrading an pre-existing urban food strategy. If the tool is used in a form of a workshop, it is suggested that someone who is already familiar with the tool moderate the discussions.

Sharing experience

The PlayDecide tool was used during a face-to-face session that involved participants of the COCOREADO ambassador network and representatives from the policymaking bodies of the city of Riga. The discussion was structured in various stages, including clustering of the cards, forming a unified policy position, sharing inspiration, and finally, creating a unified vision by focusing on the most important element(s) for the first stages of development of the UFS. It facilitated open discussions thorough exploration of diverse viewpoints when talking about food policy. To illustrate, during the discussion some groups focused on food waste, while others focused more on the role of the community. It served as a catalyst for constructive conversations, enabling participants to critically reflect on challenges and opportunities before arriving at decisions.

The emphasis on integrating various viewpoints, facilitated by this tool, reflects an integrative approach that encourages complexity in decision-making. By engaging in this participatory and integrative process, the participants were better equipped to develop a comprehensive and inclusive vision for the UFS of Riga.

Annex: Examples of three urban food strategies

As an inspiring reference, we present three examples of urban food strategies in Belgium, UK, and Italy. The ideas represented in these urban food strategies can be used to develop or improve local food policies of other European cities.

Table 1 provides a summarized overview of the main aspects of each city's UFS.

City	Ghent (Belgium)	Bristol (UK)	Rome (Italy)
Population density	1 700 people/km ²	4 022 people/km ²	City: 2 133 people/km ² Metropolitan region: 787 people/km ²
Name of UFS	Gent en garde	Feeding Bristol	Roma Food Policy
When MUFPP signed	2015	2018	2015
Start of UFS	2013	2011	2021
Participatory approach	<u>Top-down:</u> developed through a participatory process involving citizens, policymakers, and other stakeholders.	<u>Bottom-up:</u> driven by strong citizen engagement and collaborative efforts among local organisations.	<u>Bottom-up:</u> developed in collaboration with stakeholders from various sectors, including farmers, NGOs, academics, and citizens.
Name of council	Food council	Bristol Food Policy Council	Food Council Rome
Key focus	Promoting sustainable food production and consumption, reducing food waste, enhancing food education and awareness, supporting local food entrepreneurship.	Enhancing food sustainability, improving food access and affordability, supporting local businesses, reducing waste.	Promoting sustainable food production, ensuring food security and access, contact with region.
Logo			

Table 1. Summary of the three cities with their urban food strategy

Ghent en Garde, the UFS from Ghent (Belgium)

Ghent has approximately 265 086 inhabitants (in 2022) with a density of 1 700 people/km². As the capital of East-Flanders, it is the third largest city in Belgium (after Antwerp and Brussels). Currently, the mayor of Ghent is from the liberal and democratic party. Ghent committed to become a climate neutral city by 2050. This climate neutral plan, also called a climate strategy, serves as an overarching plan for many public and private actions. Food is one emergent focus in this strategy. The policy agreement for 2013–2018 included the aim of establishing an urban food strategy with a clear focus on local food initiatives and urban agriculture, making Ghent the first Belgian city with a food strategy.

The city is characterized by a lack of farmland and space to develop and sustain the farming sector. Still, Ghent has diverse efforts (e.g. organic farmer's markets, vegetarian capital of Europe since 2009, Thursday veggie-day) from local actors, such as autonomous citizens, civil society initiatives, innovative farmers, and companies (Crivits et al., 2016).

Since the 1990s, there has been a growing interest in alternative food networks. One notable example is ProVeg, formerly known as EVA (Ethical Vegetarian Alternative), an NGO dedicated to raising awareness about the advantages of vegetarianism. ProVeg originated from a group in Ghent and has been actively promoting a movement called 'Thursday veggie-day' since 2009. This campaign encourages the public to refrain from consuming meat or fish at least one day a week, with the aim of improving both individual health and the health of the planet. The initiative gained momentum rapidly and inspired other cities in Belgium and around the world to follow suit. Today, the 'Thursday veggie-day' concept is embraced in various locations, including Sao Paulo (Brazil), Bremen (Germany), Washington (USA), San Francisco (USA), Cape Town (South Africa), and more.

Only in 2013, Gent-en-Garde, the urban food strategy of Ghent, was launched. They proposed 5 strategic goals and founded a food council. Today, this council has around 30 partners. In 2018, the council received their own budget of €300,000 (over a six-year period). Still, Crivits et al. (2016) state that this budget is inadequate to meet the five strategic goals. Despite the small budget, actions have been undertaken, such as providing space to urban agriculture initiatives or participating in international projects that generate money for the urban food strategy. At the same time, Crivits et al. (2016) state that more weight should be given to physical resources (e.g., providing land and space for food hubs) and non-physical resources (e.g., communication, time, participation, and inclusion) for the support of the UFS. Eight years after the launch of the UFS, in 2021, the strategic goals were updated. In the updated version, they work around 3 strategic goals:

1. Short and sustainable food supply chain
2. Everyone eats sustainable
3. Nothing goes to waste

Example of putting strategic goals of the UFS into action: In the summer, there is a 10 day festival in the city, Gentse Feesten. They made a bold decision to have 50% of the food vendors be vegetarian options, which made quite a commotion in the city. As you can see, this didn't come about overnight, it took time to come to the point that they are now.

Figure 1. Timeline of actions made in relation to the UFS of Ghent (BE)

Who feeds Bristol? And food inequality strategy as the UFS from Bristol (UK)

Bristol is the largest city of southwest England and has approximately 467 000 inhabitants (in 2021), with a density of 4 022 people/km². The southwest has the greatest concentration (38%) of organic producers of anywhere in UK. Still, like any other city in the UK, Bristol is almost completely dependent on four large food supply companies (Tesco, Morrisons, Sainsbury's and Morrisons) (Carey, 2013).

Bristol City Council established Bristol Food Links in 1997/8 as part of its own Sustainable City team activities. Over the years Bristol Food Links evolved into Bristol Food Network, moving from a fully funded Council initiative to a voluntary sector network with its own website and newsletter, supported by the Council. In addition to Bristol Food Links, the Council's own main food interventions have been to establish Bristol Farmers' Market in 1997 (the second in the UK following Bath), promote the uptake of allotments, and more recently, sustainable food procurement. The Soil Association (started in 1946) is a charity campaigning for healthy, fair, and sustainable food, farming, and land use. They certified 70% of organic food in the UK. They support work on school and hospital meals through its Food for Life pilot work since 2004, followed by the development of the Food for Life partnership and catering mark (Soil Association, n.d.). This is an independent endorsement that awards and recognises food providers who are taking steps to improve the food they serve. For many years already, the civil society movement around food in Bristol has been strong (Halliday & Barling, 2018). Beyond these interventions, however, the local food agenda has remained largely a concern of the voluntary sector, with their focus on food growing, skills development and food access. (Carey, 2013).

Figure 3 shows a timeline focusing on the movements that had an impact on the UFS. In contrast to Ghent, they started with creating a Food Policy Council. Furthermore, Bristol is largely driven by the voluntary sector. There is a shared set of values around a vision of sustainability, which is focused on care for nature, protection of diversity, concern for community health, empowerment, and inclusion.

'Who Feeds Bristol?' is the first report that was created and it provides baseline information and evidence to inform plans and actions that will improve the resilience of the food system. The report shows that Bristol has a wealth of local producers, wholesalers, processors, caterers, and shopkeepers, and there is a strong network of community groups, organizations, and businesses interested in good, sustainably produced food (Carey, 2013). This report also shows that Bristol has different opportunities for improvement, such as energy use and carbon emissions in this food system. Another report, a Good Food Plan 2020, promotes system change and offers practical solutions to the complex issue of food provisioning in Bristol (Halliday & Barling, 2018).

In 2022, they made a strategy to fight against the food inequality in Bristol, as one in every 20 households in Bristol face stress to access adequate food. In this Food Equality Strategy (2022-2032), they focus on 6 strategic work programmes always linked with different actions (Khaled, 2022):

1. Fair, equitable access
2. Choice and security
3. Skills and resources
4. Sustainable local food system
5. Food at the heart of decision-making
6. Cross-cutting strategic aims

BRISTOL, UK

In 2018:

*Signed the MUFPP
*Bristol city council passed
Good Food and catering
Procurement policy

In 2021:
Golden standard for
Sustainable Food city

Figure 2. Timeline of actions made in relation to the UFS of Bristol (UK)

Food policy Rome, the UFS from Rome (Italy)

The city of Rome has 2.9 million inhabitants with a density of 2 133 people/km², whereas the population in the metropolitan region is approximately 4.3 million (with a density of 787 people/km²).

The city of Rome is the most populated commune in Italy. But on the other hand, it has the second largest agricultural municipality in Europe. In this context, the relationship between the city and the countryside is fundamental in terms of the urban food policies (Minotti et al., 2022).

Figure 4 shows the timeline of different actions of Rome's UFS. As in many parts of Europe, the interest in different alternative food networks grew in the 90s. In 2014, the Eating City Conference was held in Rome, where they have built a platform. The aim of the Eating City platform was to create opportunities for international meeting, to elaborate on case studies and publications with concrete proposals useful for public and private decision makers. They worked upstream and downstream of the food supply chain, together with the food industry and food service operators and buyers. After signing the MUFPP, they wrote the Strategic Metropolitan Plan, intending to create a development strategy for the area (Minotti et al., 2022).

In 2018 a participation process was launched, named 'Towards a food policy for Rome'. The food council was named Rome Food Policy and involves more than 50 organisations. In 2021, they approved the Food Policy for Rome, a working document with 10 priorities:

1. Access to primary resources (especially land, water, and agrobiodiversity)
2. Sustainable agriculture and biodiversity (sustaining organic agriculture and agroecology)
3. Short supply chains and local markets
4. City–countryside relations (integration between different phases of the supply chain, special focus on the Green Public Procurement)
5. Food and territory (strengthening territorial labelling systems, testing a traceability system for the supply chain)
6. Waste and redistribution (sustain leftovers redistribution)
7. Promoting multifunctionality (involving the disadvantaged in the process, therapeutic agriculture, agritourism)
8. Raising awareness among citizens (food and environmental education)
9. Landscape protection (contrasting soil consumption)
10. Resilience planning (agroecosystems as central elements of infrastructures, quantification of agrosilvopastoral systems' services)

ROME, IT

Figure 3. Timeline of actions made in relation to the UFS of Rome (IT)

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COCOREADO H2020 PROJECT

FOOD SYSTEM INNOVATOR TOOLKIT

CH5 Developing an idea into business

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- 3 Start defining the project
- 4 Defining the business model

5.1- Introduction

Seed initiatives involve preliminary ideas, not yet implemented in practice, whose objective is to improve the position of the farmer in the food chain and to create win-wins for producers and consumers.

This chapter presents the tools used in the COCOREADO ambassador training programme which aim to develop seed initiatives. It covers everything from fleshing out a preliminary idea to an initial definition of the business model.

In the following points, each of the tools is explained as a guide for their use.

5.2- Giving shape to an idea

To tackle food system challenges and induce sustainable transformations in food chains, new solutions that address both technical and social aspects of food-related processes are needed. During recent decades numerous initiatives have been launched at different levels, from very local to international, that propose a range of new conceptual and practical approaches to think about food and organize food chains. On the basis of the experience of seed initiatives, in this section we consider the development of novel local food initiatives which reconnect farmers and consumers and re-balance farmers' position in food chains.

1. What do you want to do? And can you get any support?

Introducing novelties in food chains implies some innovativeness. Likely, similar new food initiatives have already been launched elsewhere, but it is equally probable that in the given local situation the initiator is a pioneer who needs to break some prevailing rules and practices, and introduce new ones. In this section, we reflect on how to start thinking about the challenges you are tackling.

A. Think about what YOU want to do

It doesn't make sense to engage in a project you do not like or are not interested in. Think about **what it is that you would want to achieve**. This might be a difficult task; however, there are ways to better engage with this:

- Think about what you are passionate about
- Get inspired from examples

Look for examples and best practices in Chapter 2 "Getting inspired from examples", and then continue gathering information online or by reaching out about practices that inspire you!

- Discuss your ideas with likeminded people

Sharing your ideas with friends will help you to test out these ideas early on. Also, you might get some support from them.

- Reach out to people who have done something similar already

B. What are the challenges of the local food systems?

To arrive at a new solution for the local food system, one needs an understanding of what its deficiencies are, and what should be improved or fixed. This understanding can be gained in various complementary ways. Direct personal experience – either personal or from other stakeholders’ feedback – probably provides the brightest insights. For a reality check, it can be useful to compare these personal experiences against available data sources.

- Talk with practitioners
- Use data to verify

Look for research and data that could help you.

- Test your idea against the problems you have identified

We offer a value proposition template (presented in Figure 1) to use in the process. It helps make the ideal future explicit, and aids in listing key elements of the initiative and the benefits or added value that the initiative can bring to the stakeholders and actors involved. The tool helps the actors articulate the common desired future and the intended value creation for all of them. In this way, the tool can stretch the ambition of the group and align stakeholders with the intended outcomes.

The template focuses on the two main goals of the COCOREADO project: improving the position of the farmer in the food chain (economical focus - upper side) and reconnecting the producer and consumer (social focus - lower side). In addition, some inspiration for key elements and possible added value are provided below the template.

Figure 1: A value proposition template to approach and consider a new initiative

C. Look for support

Searching for support will look different depending on the initiative and the region; however, two essential elements that are sometimes overlooked are:

- Building alliances to collect the needed resources and skills;
- Looking for financial instruments

2. How to realise the initiative? What instruments can help me plan?

If you have reached this point, we assume you already have the idea you would want to work with, and have done some thinking about how the initiative will work. So now it's time to test the initiative and make sure that it can actually be functional and has the elements needed to survive. To this end, we recommend using a **collaboration model** – a set of exercises that allow you to structurally check what you will do.

To ensure that you benefit fully from these exercises, conduct this exercise in a group. Invite people who might be interested in the initiative and people who are competent in the issues that the initiative is addressing. Invite them to define the answers together.

Figure 2: The overall structure of the collaboration model.

"We want to create an Educational Unit in schools related to farms, rural ecosystem and food production process, including farm visits and farm products sales. To implement all this, the tools used in the trainings have been very useful."

Aitor Azkarate
"Farmers are our teachers" seed initiative, Spain

5.3- Start defining the project

Identify:

- Purpose
- Skills and capacities needed
- Key groups/actors and value statement
- Preconditions and assumptions
- Roadmap for transition: actors involved and actions by each stage of the idea.

A. Purpose: Why are you working on this project?

Use the tools provided to answer two main questions:

- Why is the initiative needed in terms of food systems? What shifts will it produce and how exactly it will help actors operating in the food systems? How will it make sure that the change is taking place?
- What personal goals do you link to the initiative? What would you expect to achieve? It's important to not lose your personal goals linked to the initiative.

B. Skills and capacities needed: What skills, competencies, and insights are needed to make the initiative work?

Now that you know what you want to achieve, try listing the skills, competencies, and insights needed to achieve this. Start by just listing everything that comes to mind. Once you have listed a number of various capacities you will need, try clustering them. What are the most important skills, competencies, and insights that are crucial to achieve the envisioned impact? Which are important but not crucial? Which are optional? Try to make a hierarchy of requirements.

If you struggle with this task, here are a couple of questions that might help you:

- Are you aware of any similar initiatives? If so, how were they organized and what problems were they dealing with?
- How will the initiative work and how will it be linked to food systems? What skills, competencies, and insights need to be there to ensure that it works?
- Do the skills and competencies listed allow the initiative to engage with the key "whys" listed in the previous step?

Why are each of the identified skills, competencies, and insights crucial for the initiative?

C. Key groups/actors and value statement: The value of the initiative

The purpose of this exercise is to identify how the world will look when the initiative is in place, after you have solved the problem. This is a challenging question because the answer might differ depending on whom you ask. So, you might start by raising the following questions:

- Who are the customers of the initiative? Which groups might benefit from the initiative?
- What problems do these groups have that the initiative will address? And how it will solve these problems?

Figure 3: Project definition steps

D. Preconditions and assumptions: Critically examine assumptions

In this step, the assumptions and preconditions that are crucial for the development of the initiative are identified. Two different exercises are proposed for this purpose.

D1. "Many uses" exercise

This method is used to generate energy, creativity, and out of the box thinking, setting the stage for innovation at a later stage. Many objects encountered on a day-to-day basis have a 'fixed' meaning and purpose assigned to them. For instance, a chair is meant for sitting, a knife for cutting, a pen for writing, and so on. This preconceived meaning is useful in terms of efficiency of everyday cognition, but it can also prevent people from looking at things with an open mind. By explicitly directing people to relate to an object in novel ways and to rethink its meaning, value, and possible purpose, new opportunities and possibilities can arise. This method can be a good way to warm up people's "creative muscles" and support them in creatively approaching more serious topics or design challenges later on during a workshop.

D2. "Sabotage" exercise

"Sabotage" exercise is a co-creation tool to identify blind spots in a project plan by taking the perspective of a saboteur. It has the potential to create strong internal support for the final project plan by stimulating divergent thinking: "What did we miss?"

Instructions:

1. The initiator of the project explains the prototype plan to the project team. The coach asks everyone (also initiators) to write on a post-it note one or two things that would make the plan fail. These can be internal or external events. As a coach, stimulate creative ideas and encourage people to point out cultural differences that could sabotage the plan.
2. Bring the group together and categorize all the ideas into clusters as you see relevant.
3. Distinguish between ideas that would be a nuisance and ideas that could really make the plan fail.

The result is a list of potential challenges, which can be considered to make or break assumptions.

D.3 Roadmap for transition

The roadmap template should be filled out with the ideal version of the initiative. This should represent the ideal form the idea would take, without being limiting by what is deemed practical at this stage.

Afterwards, the next step is to work backwards from the ideal version to consider what intermediate stages there could be in order to reach the ideal version, on the top row x-axis of the template. Which actors are involved at different levels should be also considered, with the fundamental actors involved in the core team on level 1, actors actively involved but not part of the core team in level 2, and actors that are not actively involved but important for the project to succeed in level 3.

How to use the tool?

1. Actor levels: Write down the names of the actors at each level.
2. Stage of idea: Describe what each stage means for your project
3. Actions: Describe the actions that need to be taken at the intersection of the stage & actors involved

	Stage 1: minimum viable	Stage 2: intermediate version	Stage 3: full version
	⇒ ⇒ ⇒ ⇒	⇒ ⇒ ⇒ ⇒	⇒ ⇒ ⇒ ⇒
Actor level 1: Farmers ⇒ ⇒ ⇒ ⇒ ⇒			
Actor level 2: Collaboration ⇒ ⇒ ⇒ ⇒ ⇒			
Actor level 3: Region ⇒ ⇒ ⇒ ⇒ ⇒			

Figure 4: Roadmap for transition

5.4- Defining the business model

In this chapter, our focus centres on the Business Model Canvas (BMC) as a key tool in shaping business strategies. As we explore the components of BMC, we also delve into the concept of systemic evaluation. This involves a structured assessment to ensure that a business model is on target. The following presents a detailed breakdown of the BMC and a proposal for a systemic evaluation to improve the strategic approach of the initiative.

A. Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) is a strategic management tool that helps shape and visualise the business model (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). It consists of nine building blocks: customer segments, value propositions, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships, and cost structure. These blocks represent the flow of what, how, and with whom value is created and how and to whom it is sold, thereby considering the possible costs and revenue flows. All the information is displayed in a one-page document, making it easy to obtain a holistic overview of the organisation. This can lead to new knowledge of your own organisation or a competitor organisation. The template is widely used in all types of businesses, including farming businesses.

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Figure 5: The Business Model Canvas

1

Value Proposition: description of product or service offering

Questions to answer:

- A. What is your offer for the customer?
- B. What combination of products & services do you offer?
- C. What needs/problems of the customer do you solve with this?
- D. What need of the target group do you solve? How do you fill the needs of the target group?
- E. What obstacle of the target group do you remove?
- F. How do you help the customer?
- G. What makes your business different from existing competitors?

2

Customer Segments: customer segments or target groups, grouped according to needs or behaviour

Questions to answer:

- A. Who are your key customers and what are their needs? Who do you focus on?
- B. Who do you want as customers and who do you not want as customers?
- C. Where do you find your customers? Where do customers come from?
- D. Who is the decision maker within your target group?
- E. What determines the buying behaviour (needs, purchasing power, spending pattern, etc.) of your customer?

3

Channels: description of way(s) of Value Proposition delivery

Questions to answer:

- A. How do you reach your customers?
- B. How do you make your customer interested in your offer?
- C. How do you reach your customers for marketing, prospecting, sales, delivery, etc.?
- D. What conditions must your company fulfil in terms of accessibility, parking facilities, accessibility, atmosphere, layout, appearance, etc.?
- E. What image do you want to project and how will you achieve this?
- F. What style (logo, slogan, decoration, etc.) will you use?

4

Customer Relationships: interactions & relationships with customers

Questions to answer:

- A. How do you establish and maintain relationships with customers?
- B. What type of relationship do you pursue with each customer segment (e.g. personal assistance, self-service, digital contact, automated service, community, cocreation)?
- C. How is contact made with the customer?
- D. When do you have contact with the customer?

5

Key Activities: activities performed to create Value Proposition

Questions to answer:

- A. What are the main activities you need to do yourself to realise your offer for the customer? Think about: research, development, marketing, logistics, sales, production, etc.
- B. What are the key actions/processes you need to undertake to:
 - Deliver your offer
 - Reach and convince your customer
 - Build and expand your customer relationship
 - Create value for yourself and your customer

6

Key Resources: assets like infrastructure, knowledge, and financial resources needed to create Value Proposition

Questions to answer:

- A. What people and resources do you need internally in your company to realise your offer for the customer?
- B. What are the key resources needed for realisation? Think about: brands, employees, knowledge, buildings, machines, financial resources, etc.

7

Key Partners: partners who deliver resources or perform activities to help you create your Value Proposition

Questions to answer:

- A. Which external strategic partners do you need to successfully produce, realise, and sell your product or service?
- B. Who do you call on additionally?
- C. What services do the partners provide?
- D. Which partners can strengthen your offer?
- E. What do your partners possess that you do not (e.g. knowledge, products, money, machines, infrastructure)?
- F. Which core activities do partners take over from you?

8

Revenue Streams: information about income generation, pricing strategies, etc.

Questions to answer:

- A. How will you make money with your concept?
- B. What are customers willing to pay for?
- C. What are customers not willing to pay for?
- D. What revenue model will you set up (that fits the chosen offering)?
- E. How will you receive revenue (e.g. subscription, lease, licence, hourly rate, project price)?
- F. How does a revenue model fit customer segment?

9

Cost Structure: costs that occur through the creation of the Value Proposition

Questions to answer:

- A. What are the costs of developing your product or service?
- B. What are the main fixed and variable costs?
- C. Why are the costs incurred?
- D. Which people and resources cost the most?
- E. Which core activities cost the most?

B. System evaluation of the initiative

Change readiness assessment tool

This is a tool to assess and monitor different dimensions of early stage or new change projects. To stimulate a systemic approach, it's clustered around four themes (strategy, governance, design, and activation), and further divided into 8 dimensions (Figure 6). It can be used as a quick internal project evaluation of capabilities, organizational readiness, innovation capacity, and team development.

The rose diagram is used to compare team development over time of the project. This can be used in proposal and funding discussions to demonstrate the capacity level associated with program management. In the early stages the strategy and design themes are more critical to success, later governance and activation become critical.

Figure 6: Change readiness assessment tool

Eight dimensions prepared in four clusters

1. THEME STRATEGY Visioning: Think about the “why” question: do you have a clear and shared why?

SCORING WHAT DOES THIS MEAN?

1. There is no shared vision and no shared mission.
2. There is a plan to work towards a vision and mission with the team.
3. There is a shared vision within the team.
4. There is a shared vision within the team, but not with the key (supply chain) actors and/or customers.
5. There is a shared vision with the team, key (supply chain) actors, and/or the customer.

2. THEME STRATEGY Advocating: Do you have a realistic roadmap for change?

SCORING WHAT DOES THIS MEAN?

1. There is no roadmap for change.
2. Only stage 3 of the roadmap (dreaming about ‘full version’ of the initiative) is filled in, the rest of the roadmap is not completed.
3. Stages (1, 2 and 3) of the roadmap are filled in. The other parts of the roadmap are not completed.
4. Stages and actors of the roadmap are filled in.
5. Stages, actors, and different actions in the roadmap are completed. The actors involved are aligned on the actions they need to take.

3. THEME GOVERNANCE Organizing: Is the team complementary (in terms of skills and the abilities of each member)? Do you have an organization structure with clear role assignment?

SCORING WHAT DOES THIS MEAN?

1. There is no team. They are still in search of complementary skills.
An example of complementary skills in a team is if one person has technical skills and another person has more business-related skills, such as marketing or communication.
2. There is a team, but they don't have complementary skills.
3. There is a team with complementary skills, but no specific roles are assigned to each member.
4. There is a team with complementary skills, each team member has a specific role assigned.
5. The skills of the team are in balance with the abilities of each member and roles are assigned.

4. THEME GOVERNANCE Financing: What financial resources are available for the initiative? Does the team have plans for attracting future funding? Are these realistic and in line with the goals of the team?

SCORING WHAT DOES THIS MEAN?

1. Financial resources are not available, the team is still in search of these resources.
2. Financial resources are available for the initiative (current costs and benefits are balanced). There is no plan for attracting future funding.
3. Financial resources are available for the initiative, and the initiative is viable (the difference between the current costs and benefits generates a net positive result). There is a plan in line with the goals for attracting future funding.
4. The team is currently working on securing future funding based on the plan.
5. Financial resources are available for the initiative and the initiative is viable. Future funding in line with the goals of the initiative has been secured.

5. THEME DESIGN Customer validation: Did the team do a customer validation of the initiative? Is there any proof that customers (or your target group) are interested and willing to pay and/or participate? It might be the case that your "customers" are not paying for your services but someone else is. In that case we refer to them as your target group.

SCORING WHAT DOES THIS MEAN?

1. The team has not identified their make-or-break assumptions.
2. The team has identified their make-or-break assumptions and talked with some potential customers or their target group who provided feedback.
3. The team has developed a method to receive feedback from a large set of customers or their target group.
4. The team has validated their idea with potential customers or their target group. They are looking into their interest and willingness to pay and participate in the initiative.
5. The team has validated their idea with customers or their target group. They have proof of their interest and willingness to pay and participate in the initiative.

6. THEME DESIGN Prototyping and scaling: Do you have a minimal viable product (MVP) or prototype to test new products and services?

SCORING WHAT DOES THIS MEAN?

1. The team has not reflected on how to validate customer interest in future products and services.
2. The team is working on a prototype/MVP to validate customer interest in future products and service.
3. There is a prototype/MVP to validate customer interest in future products and services.
4. The prototype/MVP is constantly adapted to new products under development.
5. The initiative can successfully launch new products and services (continue innovating) in a cost-effective manner.

7. THEME ACTIVATION Measuring and evaluating: Do you have processes in place to monitor and evaluate your initiative?

SCORING WHAT DOES THIS MEAN?

1. The team has no processes in place to monitor and evaluate the initiative. There is also no intention to set up these processes
2. The team is experimenting with different tools to monitor and evaluate their performance but has not set up a structure for implementation.
3. The team has selected some tools and is now developing a structured approach: who needs to complete what tool and when.
4. The team has selected a set of tools and developed processes to monitor and evaluate their performance.
5. The team has tools and processes to monitor and evaluate the initiative. The outcome of these evaluations is actively used to improve the performance of the project.

8. THEME ACTIVATION Communication: Does the initiative have a clear communication strategy based on the vision?

SCORING WHAT DOES THIS MEAN?

1. There are no clear communication objectives, no clear target audience, no communication messages, and no channels have been identified.
2. The key communication objectives are identified but no target audience, no communication messages, and no channels have been identified.
3. The key communication objectives are identified, as well as the target audience. The communication message and channels are still lacking.
4. The key communication objectives are identified as well as the target audience and clear messages adapted to these target audiences. The communication channels are still lacking.
5. The key communication objectives are identified, as well as the target audience, and clear messages adapted to these target audiences and appropriate communication channels. This is combined in a coherent communication plan.

"The aim of the Food Hub is to give farmers various services as processing or packaging of their products, increasing their added value. Tools as Business Model Canvas and systemic evaluation helped me to better define the business model and priorities, before starting to implement the project."

*Bledar Meta
"Food Hub Albania" seed initiative, Albania*

FOOD SYSTEM INNOVATOR TOOLKIT

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